

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

COMADRE DISCUSSIONS: A CULTURALLY SENSITIVE INTERVENTION TO
IMPROVE GESTATIONAL DIABETES OUTCOMES IN HISPANIC WOMEN

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Noemi Barajas

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Maria Matza, PhD, RN, CNS, PHN, Project Chair
Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN, Committee Member

May 2019

Copyright Noemi Barajas 2019 ©

ABSTRACT

Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM) affects more than 25 % of Hispanic women in the United States (Sacks et al., 2012). Hyperglycemia in pregnancy contributes to poor maternal-fetal outcomes. Adherence to GDM management is an ongoing problem for healthcare providers and patients. Once the diagnosis is confirmed, standard management includes non-pharmacological and pharmacological regimens. Management focuses on diet modification, and exercise. In addition to the standard Sweet Success curriculum, adherence to GDM management may improve by using culturally sensitive discussion sessions.

The purpose of this quality improvement project was to add *Comadre* discussions to the standardized educational program in the primary setting for Hispanic GDM's women to improve perinatal outcomes for both mother and baby. The Culturally Competent Change Theory (CCCT) model was used to pilot this quality improvement project. Two supporting frameworks guided the model: Campinha-Bacote's cultural competence model (Campinha-Bacote, 2002) and Kurt Lewin's Model of Change (Lewin, 1951).

Preliminary findings compared two groups one the *Comadres* ($n = 10$) and the retrospective group non-participants ($n = 10$). Descriptive statistics indicated participants ages ranged from 18-35 (mean 27.2 [SD 6.2]) for the *Comadres* group. Non-participant group ages ranged from 24-35 (mean 30.2 [SD 3.8]) years. Monitoring of weight gain

from start of prenatal care to current gestational weeks revealed range weight of 6 to 36 pounds with a mean weight gain of 14 pounds for the *Comadres* group compared to minus 2 to 75 pounds with a mean weight gain of 24.3 pounds.

At this point in time, there is insufficient evidence that the *Comadre* classes are affecting blood sugar maintenance (mean 106.4 mg/dL [*SD* 9.42] to mean 107.7 mg/dL [7.08]). Although the impact of blood glucose measures was not statistically significant, there was less weight gain in the *Comadres* group. Despite the lack of change in blood sugar results, the *Comadres* revealed behavior change in tracking their blood sugars.

Qualitative findings were useful in identifying internal and external factors to change behaviors. *Comadre* discussions were useful to build rapport and share the women's experience of their daily struggles to manage their diet, monitor blood sugars and barriers to health care adherence.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	ix
BACKGROUND	1
Management of Gestational Diabetes.....	2
Local Context.....	4
Purpose Statement.....	5
Project Objectives.....	5
Supporting Framework	6
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	11
Pathophysiology.....	13
Culturally Sensitive Interventions to Improve Management.....	14
Standard Education for GDM.....	14
Diet Adherence	15
Exercise Adherence	17
Health Beliefs of Pregnant Hispanics	17
Group Learning.....	18
Innovative Teaching Methods for Hispanic Patients.....	20
Summary.....	21
METHODS	22
Setting.....	23
Sample	23
Ethical Issues	24
Planning the Quality Improvement Project	24
Methods of Evaluation.....	25
Group Discussion Guide.....	25
Discussion Sessions	26
Data Analysis.....	26

FINDINGS.....	28
DISCUSSION.....	31
Weight Gain.....	31
Blood Sugar Control.....	33
Qualitative Results.....	34
Summary.....	42
Limitations.....	42
CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	44
REFERENCES.....	46
APPENDIX A: CLINICAL DIRECTOR APPROVAL.....	60
APPENDIX B: CONSENTS.....	61
APPENDIX C: COMMUNITY ANNOUNCEMENT.....	68
APPENDIX D: DISCUSSION GUIDE QUESTIONS.....	69
APPENDIX E: DISCUSSION GUIDE QUESTIONS (SPANISH).....	70
APPENDIX F: SAMPLE OF CLASS HANDOUTS.....	71
APPENDIX G: DELIVERY OUTCOMES.....	77
APPENDIX H: TABLES OF EVIDENCE.....	78

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Campinha-Bacote's Construct	7
2. Database Searches.....	12
3. Timeline of Tasks	25
4. Descriptive Statistics: Comadres and Non-Participants	29

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Culturally Competent Change Theory.....	9

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Thank you, Lord, for my health, guidance, knowledge, and strength You have bestowed on me. Without Your grace and blessings, I would have never accomplished my goals. Faith kept me sane and diligent.

To my family, especially my five children; Jesse, Steve, Brian, Julien and Lauren whom I love dearly, thank you for all your patience, love and understanding. In many ways, each one of you has inspired me during my many hours of study, and always understood that education is worthwhile and takes away from family outings and gatherings. Special thanks to my mother Ramona who inspired me to get an education in this great country of opportunity. “Mom, I went to school for you since you were not permitted to get the education you desired, this is as much yours as mine.” To my husband Dr. Raymond A. Barajas for the unconditional love and support you have provided throughout this and many journeys. To my siblings, Adrian, Everardo, and Rose thank you for your understanding when I could not be around during the family times.

To three strong and wise women who have always believed and supported me in many ways. Dr. M. Matza, Dr. P. Weissmuller, and Dr. D. Rutledge your guidance and knowledge is greatly appreciated.

Lastly, to all my friends and relatives who may not have understood what I was doing all this time. Thank you for all your love and encouragement.

BACKGROUND

In 2014, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring Systems reported a rise in the United States (U.S.) for deliveries among women with Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM). Gestational Diabetes is intolerance of carbohydrates that occur during pregnancy, which causes an increase in blood glucose (sugar) levels (CDC, 2014). Hispanics are the third largest ethnic group in the United States with 12.8% diagnosed with diabetes (CDC, 2015). In the Hyperglycemia and Adverse Pregnancy Outcome (HAPO) Study, it was reported that greater than 25% of Hispanic women suffered from GDM (Sacks et al., 2012).

Gestational diabetes is responsible for poor maternal and fetal outcomes. Negative perinatal outcomes include stillbirth, preeclampsia, and premature delivery (Mocarski & Savitz, 2012; Sweeting et al., 2016). During the intrapartum period, GDM mothers are at risk for a primary cesarean section due to the increased size of their newborns (Wong, Ross, Jalaludin, & Flack, 2013). After delivery, 15 to 50% of women with GDM will develop Type II Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) (Landon & Nicholson, 2013). Hispanic women with GDM have a higher rate of developing T2DM within five years of delivery than do non-Hispanic women (Bellamy, Casas, Hingorani, & Williams, 2009; Kjos et al., 1995).

Post-delivery, newborns of GDM mothers are at risk for hypoglycemia, jaundice, and respiratory problems (Dabelea et al., 2008; Fung et al., 2014; Palatnik et al., 2015) as well as long-term adverse health outcomes. For example, these infants are at risk for obesity, poor visual acuity, and T2DM (Metzger, 2007).

Management of Gestational Diabetes

Recommendations for standard screening for diagnosis is from 24-28 weeks of gestation unless there are other risk factors to initiate earlier in the pregnancy (Caughey & Turrentine, 2018). Once GDM is diagnosed, standard management includes non-pharmacological and pharmacological regimens, diet modification, and exercise. Weight is monitored throughout prenatal care. Diabetes management guidelines are guided by the American Diabetic Association (ADA) and advocate for lifestyle management by means of “Diabetes Self-Management Education and Support (DSMES)” as part of their recommended national standards (ADA, 2018, p. S38). This association also recommends a carbohydrate-managed diet with GDM. Medication management may include oral hypoglycemic agents or parenteral insulin (Landon & Nicholson, 2013). Monitoring of standard laboratory tests includes thyroid panel, standard prenatal markers, daily blood glucose testing, and glycosylated hemoglobin or HbA1c (ADA, 2016).

Healthcare providers are managing GDM with varying degrees of success. Palatnik et al. (2015) studied whether early gestation treatment of GDM would result in better perinatal outcomes. Through this study, the authors saw no difference in outcomes if interventions began earlier or later in pregnancy. Sweeting et al. (2016) also concluded that traditional early testing and recommended management did not result in better perinatal outcomes. As a result, both groups concluded that all high-risk pregnancies continue to contribute to poor pregnancy outcomes (Palatnik et al., 2015; Sweeting et al., 2016).

Typically, in the U.S., women with GDM, including Hispanics, are given traditional diabetic patient education as part of a standard intervention. This standardized curriculum provided in a given setting may or may not be culturally appropriate.

In California, the management of GDM begins with a referral from the interdisciplinary team to the California Diabetes and Pregnancy Program (CDAPP) called Sweet Success (<http://www.cdappsweetsuccess.org>). Also, referrals are made to a perinatologist to assist with the high-risk pregnancy. The health care provider counsels' patients regarding the risk of congenital and genetic disorders due to their GDM. The perinatologist oversees obstetric management due to the high-risk status of pregnant mothers with GDM. The purpose of the CDAPP Sweet Success Program is to improve and promote positive fetal and maternal birth outcomes through health education to prevent the development of chronic disease (Shields & Tsay, 2015). Education involves information on healthy eating, being active, monitoring blood sugar, taking medications, problem-solving, reducing risks, and healthy coping behaviors (Shields & Tsay, 2015). Additionally, nutritional counseling by a Registered Dietitian is often recommended (Landon & Nicholson, 2013).

Adherence to GDM management may be improved by using a culturally delivered teaching or discussions methodology in addition to the standard Sweet Success curriculum. Successful Hispanic culturally relevant community models for health education and support do exist. These programs offer patient navigation, health education, as well as peer support. Two examples are the *Comadre* model used by the University of New Mexico (<https://comadre.unm.edu>), and the *Cafecitos* model used in Orange County, California by Susan J. Komen (Komen, 2017). These community models

incorporate Hispanic/Latino cultural values of respect, personalism, and family, as well as a shared decision-making type of model that allows the clients to share mutual concerns. The use of *Comadre* role-model education sessions as discussions to teach culturally sensitive interventions may improve responsiveness to GDM management. *Comadres* are supportive friends who are well known to most Hispanics; they share values, role-model to others, and share similar values (Gill-Hopple, 2010). In the Hispanic culture, *Comadres* are chosen to be *madrinas* (godmothers) by parents. The *Comadre* is also known as a “non-biological close female kinship that exists in the Hispanic/Latino extended family unit” (Duval, 2013, p.15). The utilization of one of these models may increase responsiveness to GDM treatment regimens for pregnant Hispanic women.

Local Context

This Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project will be implemented in a San Gabriel Valley prenatal clinic in Los Angeles County with an estimated population of 115,665. According to the U.S. Census Bureau, 65.7% of residents in a focused area of the San Gabriel Valley reported their ethnicity as Hispanic or Latino descent of any race (United States Census Bureau, 2015).

Patients are seen in a small outpatient clinic located within a small shopping center. Once diagnosis and management are established, the standard of care for GDM patients follows the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG) guidelines and recommendations (Rouse, 2014). Currently, two to three health care providers implement minimal dietary teaching; no registered dietician (R.D.) is available in the clinic. Nutrition and exercise are the primary teaching foci of clinic providers. A

referral to Sweet Success was done for all GDM patients with the expectation that for this project the *Comadres* educational intervention was provided for some of the clinic patients.

In the project setting, approximately 85% of patients are Spanish-speaking only. The local Sweet Success Program does not appear to be tailored to the unique needs of this diverse population of Hispanics. Patients report little teaching in Spanish (only in English) and that the recommended dietary changes do not include foods they routinely eat. Thus, the recommended program diet may not meet the cultural needs of the Hispanic patient (Carolan-Olah, Duarte-Gardea, Lechuga, & Salinas-Lopez, 2017). Sometimes, patients report that attending the program is a waste of their time. The current practice of referral to Sweet Success thus creates a gap in meeting the language and educational needs of Hispanics with GDM.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this quality improvement project was to add *Comadre* discussions to the standardized educational program in the primary setting for Hispanic GDM's women to improve perinatal outcomes for both mother and baby.

Project Objectives

Aims for this project were to:

- Provide and implement a culturally sensitive and appropriate discussion sessions provided during regular prenatal office visits. Topics included diet, exercise and emotional reactions of living with GDM.
- Empower patients to create self-awareness through reflection by facilitation of culturally appropriate discussions with a bilingual/bi-cultural nurse practitioner.

- Compare clinical outcomes of GDM mothers by evaluating intermittent maternal glucose levels, maternal weight levels, birthweight, type of delivery, and NICU admission with those who have received only the Sweet Success standard education and those who received the culturally-delivered *Comadre* discussions.

Supporting Framework

Two supporting frameworks guided the project: Josepha Campinha-Bacote's cultural competence model (Campinha-Bacote, 2002) and Kurt Lewin's Model of Change (Lewin, 1951). Integrating cultural competence while making a change will help the health care provider develop a teaching intervention that will be more acceptable to patients who are being asked to change their behaviors. Lewin's Change Model will assist the patients to unfreeze their health beliefs and cultural attitudes. Subsequently, the adapted (re-frozen) cultural response will produce benefit for both patient and provider (Campinha-Bacote, 2002).

Campinha-Bacote's model supports *Comadre* discussions by considering the five constructs (Table 1) that connect the process of cultural competency in care delivery (Campinha-Bacote, 2002, p. 181). The five constructs interconnect to meet the "The Process of Cultural Competence". Campinha-Bacote's model is useful as a comprehensive guide for educational intervention development (Albougami, Pounds, & Alotaibi, 2016). Integrating the five constructs of the model will facilitate the educator in teaching Hispanic women in a more sensitive manner to make desired behavioral changes and to re-freeze the newly learned behaviors.

In this project, discussions were offered to Hispanic women with GDM in culturally appropriate *Comadre* sessions. A Family Nurse Practitioner (FNP) was the

health provider and facilitator of the group. The commonality of GDM, language, and ethnicity unified the group to incorporate the five constructs of cultural competence. The first focus was to build a rapport through the relationship formed between provider and patient, and other members of the discussion group. During the transition phase (unfreezing) when patients were exposed to new information including recommendations, the FNP will utilize the Culturally Competent Change Theory (CCCT) model (Figure 2) in order to provide a culturally competent education program (Campinha-Bacote, 2002, p. 183). In other words, the provider (as facilitator) educated the women by focusing on her own:

Table 1

Campinha-Bacote's Construct

1. Cultural Awareness	Provider awareness of own cultural beliefs
2. Cultural Skills	Provision of a culturally sensitive biological and psychosocial assessment
3. Cultural Knowledge	Provider awareness of maternal beliefs about GDM, heredity, myths, and faith
4. Cultural Encounters	Experiences between provider and mothers to include appropriate physical assessment & non-judgmental health history
5. Cultural Desire	Provider desires to gain cultural awareness and provide transcultural patient care interactions

Adapted from *The Process of Cultural Competence in the Delivery of Health Care Services* (Campinha-Bacote, 2002)

In all appropriate interactions, the provider shared information about diet and exercise goals. Before making specific recommendations for change, the provider assessed women's usual or acceptable food choices and exercise ways. For example, if the patient's usual breakfast was fried eggs with salsa and refried beans, they were educated to poach the eggs, add the salsa, and smash the beans without frying with fatty oils. For enhanced exercise, they were coached to walk their children to school instead of driving them. The proposed discussion sessions were the action plan. The evaluation for unfreezing included the aforementioned clinical measures.

The middle boxes in Figure 2 suggest the ways to alter the driving and restraining forces to change behavior using Campinha-Bacote's constructs. Culturally competent discussions were funneled during the process of unfreezing to change behaviors.

Kurt Lewin's Change Model was used to view change once the culturally sensitive intervention was implemented. The actions of using cultural competency guided the elements that are necessary to change health behaviors. Lewin's model focuses on the concept of managing change. A block of ice is used as an analogy to represent how behaviors can be shaped and molded by freezing and unfreezing (Figure 1). The Unfreeze-Change-Refreeze paradigm examines GDM's current behaviors and how they can be reshaped into new behaviors, which should lead to healthier maternal and neonatal outcomes. New behaviors of interest were used as the focus to have GDM patients make better food choices and increase their exercise (Lewin, 1951).

Figure 1. Culturally Competent Change Theory (CCCT). Adapted from Kurt Lewin change model (Lewin, 1951) and The Process of Cultural Competence in the Delivery of Health Care Services (Campinha-Bacote, 2002).

Traditional forms of teaching may not change Hispanic patients' perceptions of how their non-adherent behaviors impact their GDM condition (Carolan-Olah, Duarte-Gardea, Lechuga, & Salinas-Lopez, 2017; Goldschmidt & Colletta, 2016). The goal of *Comadre*-style discussion sessions is to connect with patients' beliefs and values and to change behaviors in order to get better outcomes. Nurses and educators can repeatedly teach content but must consider innovative and appropriate ways of making true connections with their patients. Lastly, in order to evaluate re-freezing and maintain behavior changes, women will be monitored until they deliver. Proactive behaviors will be reinforced using cultural values and familism. This step was reinforced by group

discussions concerning diet, exercise and general feelings of GDM. This will be further reinforced by the health outcomes for the entire family that is incorporated by a healthy diet and family recreation. Another benefit of the *Comadre* sessions will be the rich cultural information offered by the patients from their discussions with the facilitator that may be shared with other providers.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of the literature was conducted to support this DNP project. Databases searched to identify applicable research and practice guidelines include PubMed, CINAHL, and Google Scholar. In addition to the database searches, reference lists from journal articles were searched to identify additional sources (Table 2).

Inclusion criteria include peer-reviewed research articles. Searches were restricted to English and Spanish language publications. There were no geographical limitations for evidence in terms of study location. Literature older than 2013 was excluded unless a seminal publication was identified. Within GDM management searches, Type I and II diabetes mellitus were excluded. Keywords and acronyms that were used for searches include gestational diabetes mellitus, GDM management, pregnant Hispanics, culturally competent patient education, lifestyle modifications, practice guidelines, and ACOG. Additionally, the conceptual framework search utilized the following keywords: change theory, behavioral frameworks, health promotion theories, and cultural competency framework. Selected research articles were organized by subject to summarize strength and evidence of selected topics of interest by construction of a table of evidence (Appendix H).

Table 2

Database Searches

Topic	Search Term	Search Term Combinations	# Found
Interventions	Gestational diabetes mellitus, culturally competent patient education	Gestational diabetes mellitus AND pregnant Latinas AND culturally competent AND patient education	CINAHL = 0 PubMed = 1 Google Scholar = 981
		GDM AND exercise	CINAHL= 108 PubMed = 1 Google Scholar 2,130
		GDM AND diet AND Hispanics	CINAHL = 6
		GDM AND exercise AND diet AND lifestyle AND California AND teaching AND interventions	After narrowing search from 2016-2018 Google Scholar = 347
		Culturally competent patient education, GDM, Latina women	
Conceptual framework	Culturally competent Theory Behavioral change theories	Change theory, behavioral, health promotion theory, and culturally competent framework.	CINAHL = 5 Google Scholar = 17, 010
		Culturally competent framework	PubMed = 17
GDM Management	California gestational diabetes mellitus management Mexico and Latin America	Practice guidelines AND GDM AND California AND ACOG	CINAHL = 0 PubMed = 0 Google Scholar = 3,230
		Mexico gestational diabetes mellitus management exclude Type II DM	CINAHL = 0 PubMed = 0 Google Scholar = 3,420
		Latin America management of GDM, exclude Type II DM	CINAHL = 0 PubMed = 0 Google Scholar = 6,800

Pathophysiology

Diabetes Mellitus is caused by a partial or complete deficiency of insulin secretion by the beta cells of the pancreas. Hyperglycemia or hypoglycemia may result when diet consumption does not match insulin secretion. GDM includes any amount of glucose intolerance identified or documented with pregnancy. This complex disorder of carbohydrate metabolism alteration affects pregnancy due to metabolic changes in early and late pregnancy. Minute changes in blood sugars usually occur on weeks 1-20 of gestation due to the stability of maternal metabolic demand and little energy needs. Subsequently, after 20 weeks the mother's metabolism increases due to the growing fetus and maternal fat accumulation. As the fetus rapidly grows, placental hormones also increase. Placental hormones that produce insulin resistance in pregnancy include estrogen, progesterone, and human placental lactogen. These hormones produce a diabetogenic effect on mother resulting in insulin resistance and increased amounts of sugar go to the baby. As a result, the mother has insufficient insulin and experiences hyperglycemia episodes (McKinney, James, Murray, Nelson, & Ashwill, 2017).

There are three types of Diabetes Mellitus that may affect pregnant women. Approximately 30.3 million people are diagnosed with diabetes in America, about 9.4% of the population. Type II diabetes is more common than Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (T1DM) or GDM (<http://www.diabetes.org/diabetes-basics/statistics/>). While women affected by either T1DM or T2DM have a higher incidence of poor perinatal outcomes, pre-existing diabetes mellitus is not common in pregnancy. In pregnant women, GDM is more common, accounting for 90% of cases compared to 8% of women who have pre-existing diabetes (Moore et al., 2018).

Culturally Sensitive Interventions to Improve Management

Professional organizations advocate for women's health improvement with practice bulletins and expert guidelines. Their goals are to continue to educate healthcare providers with updated evidence-based practices for the standard of care (Hartling et al., 2012). Guidelines are meant to improve how patient treatments are guided but unfortunately, may not necessarily improve patient management or adherence to a regimen if teaching and learning do not match.

Racial and ethnic disparities continue to limit minorities from receiving equal health care. The Institute of Medicine (IOM) recommendation to improve disproportionate treatment in health care is the development of culturally appropriate education for targeted groups (Smedley, Stith, & Nelson, 2003, p.198). Culturally appropriate education should improve patient participation, knowledge, self-advocacy, decision making with care, and care-seeking skills (Smedley, Stith, & Nelson, 2003). This suggests that health care providers should have awareness and use culturally tailored interventions to provide competent care (Thorlby, Jorgensen, Ayanian, & Sequist, 2011) (see Appendix F). Thorlby et al. (2011) suggested health care providers not only to use standard methods to improve GDM adherence but to focus on culturally tailored dietary and exercise advice and to account for socioeconomic factors.

Standard Education for GDM

Once GDM is diagnosed, a standardized treatment regimen focuses on changing diet and exercise practices and incorporates glucose monitoring. Diet management is important to control glucose levels; if control is not achieved, medication therapy is started.

Diet Adherence

Recommendations for dietary counseling for GDM include 20-33% of complex carbohydrates, 20% of protein, and 40% of non-saturated fats (Caughey & Turrentine, 2018). Experts suggest limited weight gain for each trimester with pregnancy and BMI to achieve better maternal and fetal outcomes, best results are seen when there are acceptable blood glucose levels throughout the pregnancy (Caughey & Turrentine, 2018; Yee, Cheng, Inturrisi, & Caughey, 2013) (see Appendix G). The objective for the interjection of the cultural dietary counseling is for better adherence to dietary guidelines for GDMs and healthy weight maintenance. Once diagnosed with GDM, blood sugars will be monitored per standard care. Blood sugar monitoring recommendations are four times per day and no less than twice per day with the following: Fasting < 95mg/dL, one hour after meals < 140mg/dL, two hours after meals, or < 120mg/dL after two hours of consuming a meal (Caughey & Turrentine, 2018). HbA1c is a poor assessment tool for GDM diagnosis or compliance during pregnancy and is infrequently used in standard of care (Fung et al., 2014; Moyer, 2014).

Contributing factors associated with the onset of GDM include maternal weight (overweight or obese), rapid weight gain during the second and the third trimester in pregnancy, diets high in fat and carbohydrates, and lack of exercise (CDC, 2015). A person is considered overweight when their BMI ranges from 25 to 30 and considered obese when the BMI is higher than 30 (CDC, 2016). Among Hispanic ethnic groups, obesity rates are slightly higher for females (38.3%) than for males (34.3%) (Ogden et al., 2015). High BMI and weight gain prior or during pregnancy continue to be leading risk factors for diabetes and cardiovascular disease in America (Flegal, Carroll, Ogden, &

Curtin, 2010; CDC, 2015). Rahman and Berenson (2010) suggest that the National Institute of Health's (NIH) BMI is an underestimation of measurement in obesity in Hispanic women when compared to using the World Health Organization (WHO) body fat percentage reference.

Carbohydrate intake is the focus to control glucose and to stay within recommended weight gain for all trimesters. Long-term intake of high carbohydrates not only affects pregnancy and baby, but also contributes to a rapid decline for insulin beta-cell compensation that may lead to T2DM (Chen, Watanabe, Stram, Buchanan, & Xiang, 2014). As a result, uncontrolled glucose and excessive weight gain in pregnancy continue to influence poor clinical outcomes for Hispanic mothers and their babies (Chasan-Taber, 2012; Goldstein et al., 2017; Landon et al., 2011).

Yee et al. (2013) investigated perinatal outcomes in obese women with GDM who were enrolled in the Sweet Success Program. The study's findings showed some improvements with newborns and mothers, such as 5.2% maternal weight loss of 4.3 pounds in third trimester, less antepartum and NICU admissions, and a decrease in large for gestational age (LGA) babies. Yet, some adverse outcomes from this study while enrolled in Sweet Success Program, included preterm deliveries and babies that are small for gestational age (SGA). The authors suggested more research into weight loss and the development of interventions to improve GDM adherence. In another study evaluating the Sweet Success Program, authors suggested that a lack of patient adherence to program regimens were due to an inappropriate "educational/literacy level" (Chung et al., 2006, p.328).

Exercise Adherence

Literature suggests that healthy eating and exercise helps prevent, control, and reduce the incidence of GDM. In a meta-analysis of randomized controlled studies, Russo et al. (2015) suggested that physical activity offers slight protection from developing GDM. Timing, duration, and compliance with exercise are important factors to be included in obstetrical guidelines (Russo et al., 2015). ACOG guidelines recommend moderate-intensity physical activity, 20-30 minutes per day, most days of the week unless contraindicated with the pregnancy (Kilpatrick, Papile, & Macones, 2017). GDM Hispanic women may struggle to adhere to recommended exercise due to barriers related to transportation or childcare (Chasan-Taber et al., 2010). In fact, in a study investigating levels of physical activity and stress in GDM Hispanic women, only 18.7% of participants met the ACOG recommended exercise regimen and 5.2% met the recommendations in early pregnancy (Chasan-Taber et al., 2010). Some women will improve-physical activity and dietary quality if counseled individually by trained nurses that are sensitive to patients' needs (Koivusalo et al., 2016).

Health Beliefs of Pregnant Hispanics

Lifestyle behaviors such as diet, exercise, and perceived disease process are associated with ethnic identity. Understanding the Hispanic experience with the diagnosis of GDM is important in determining and investigating strategies that may contribute to successful teaching modalities. Carolan-Olah, Duarte-Gardea, Lechuga, and Salinas-Lopez (2017) investigated five themes of the experience of Mexican women dealing with GDM. The themes included “(1) distress and fear; (2) realizing the changes required; (3) learning to manage GDM; (4) finding motivation; and (5) compliance despite limited

understanding” (p.16). From these five themes, the researchers found that the participants made necessary dietary and exercise changes to manage their GDM for the best interest of their babies.

Considering beliefs of how and why the Hispanic woman believes she acquired GDM should be considered when providing teaching. The folk medicine and magical-religious beliefs old folks supernatural medicinal of *susto* (fright sickness), *mal de ojo* (evil eye), or *coraje* (anger) still exist in many Hispanic women (Gobiel, 1973; Lemley & Spies, 2014). Women may also share the belief that getting diabetes is a curse, or a punishment from God because of a wrong-doing (Giacinto, 2016).

Mother-daughter relationships have had success in teaching interventions for Hispanic women (Sorkin et al., 2013). Females of the household are usually the ones who do the shopping and prepare meals in the Hispanic household. Thus, women play an important role to promote behavioral changes with diet and exercise routines. Weight loss behavioral programs such as *Unidas por la Vida* (united for life) for Hispanic women promote weight loss while achieving satisfaction by having individuals work together as a family group (Sorkin et al., 2013).

Group Learning

Group teaching compared to individual educational interventions appears favorable for Hispanics. Diabetes self-management education is the standard educational programs to provide evidence-based education for all diabetes educators (ADA, 2018; Funnell et al., 2009).

Several studies show that barriers impeding Hispanic individuals from healthier lifestyles may be expressed best amongst group sessions. Brown et al. (2015)

successfully implemented focus groups in the workplace to promote diabetes prevention programs for Hispanic employees. This study identified one principle message from participants of identifying the importance of taking care of their health with family and work responsibilities. In a subsequent study with Mexican Americans living along the Texas-Mexico border, Brown et al. (2018) supported the importance of positive group learning from persons diagnosed with prediabetes and T2DM. Additionally, study results demonstrated motivational behavioral changes for diabetes prevention from group classes of 7-12 participants (Brown et al., 2018). Another study utilized focused group discussions with three different cultures that included Hispanics, African Americans and the Appalachians resulting in similar outcomes using group discussions. These discussions generated themes about barriers in accessing care for GDMs, management, and post-partum follow-up. Twelve sessions of four participants per race-ethnic groups resulted in identifying barriers of communication, environmental barriers, and type and quality of healthcare (Oza-Frank, Conrey, Bouchard, Shellhaas, & Weber, 2018).

Key points to consider when planning discussion sessions to a targeted population are whether to use group or individual teaching sessions and interventions when providing prenatal care. One study suggested that educational interventions are dependent on the method of instruction rather than a group or individual format (Schellinger et al., 2017). Schellinger et al. (2017) found improved clinical outcomes with GDM women with grouped prenatal care using the “Centering Pregnancy” model (p. 297) versus traditional individual prenatal care. Women who received the group prenatal care were more likely to initiate and implement strict breastfeeding. Additionally, they were more likely to return for postpartum glucose monitoring (83.6 % vs. 60.7 %; $p = 0.04$).

Trudnak, Arboleda, Kirby, & Perrin (2013) saw no significant changes in small birth weights with the Centering Pregnancy model with either group but did find improved utilization of healthcare.

In a systematic review of individual versus group prenatal care, Homer et al. (2012) described better outcomes with a consistent provider rather than subsequent encounters with multiple providers. This study demonstrated a satisfaction rate five times higher with group prenatal care in the Centering Pregnancy trial compared to one-to-one provider prenatal care. This may extend to the focused discussion and creating teaching-learning opportunities utilizing *Comadre* group sessions with one healthcare provider who is culturally and linguistically competent (Homer et al., 2012; McCurley et al., 2017).

Innovative Teaching Methods for Hispanic Patients

Educational programs that attract and connect patients to educators should emphasize cultural beliefs and traditions to better engage learners. The *Compadrazgo* experience has existed in Latin America since the Spanish brought Catholicism to the New World (Gill-Hopple, 2010). This system expands the definition of the nuclear and extended family to include close friends, especially the special friendships women share. The *Comadre Project* concept continues to embrace educational outreach for breast cancer education and support for Hispanic women in New Mexico and Southern California (Duval, 2003; Komen, 2017; Saavedra, 2017). Individual and group support using comadre concepts continues to be a successful intervention in supporting cancer patients and their loved ones (Duval, 2003; Rayle, Sand, Brucato, & Ortega, 2006; Saavedra, 2017). *Cafecitos* (coffee gatherings) and *telenovelas* (soap operas) are other successful, culturally tailored

interventions that have had success with the Hispanic population. Janice Crist used two concepts of informal discussions to engage and teach elder Latinos and caregivers to improve home care services (Crist, 2005). *Dulce Mothers* (sweet mothers) is another low-cost and effective intervention for diabetes prevention in Southern California (Philis-Tsimikas et al., 2014). *Dulce Mothers* is a primary prevention program designed for low-income Spanish-speaking Hispanic women with a history of GDM. Goals were to reduce the incidence of T2DM and cardiovascular disease. This culturally tailored peer-led-educator approach improved lifestyle behaviors, blood pressure, and lipid levels.

Summary

The literature strongly supports the need to provide culturally sensitive group session interventions when trying to promote behavior changes such as those recommended for mothers who have GDM. Studies which evaluate non-culturally sensitive strategies show poor outcomes in the domain of diet and exercise and a lack of adherence by Hispanic GDM patients. These may reflect a deficiency in providers' cultural knowledge base as to the importance of cultural foods and health practices in the Hispanic community. Therefore, a culturally derived and applied GDM intervention for Hispanic women may ameliorate this disparity.

METHODS

The purpose of this quality improvement project was to improve perinatal outcomes including intermittent maternal glucose levels, maternal weight levels, newborn birth weight, type of delivery, and neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admission in Hispanic women diagnosed with GDM. In this project, the project lead implemented culturally sensitive discussion sessions as a support to the standard Sweet Success GDM educational curriculum. The evaluation was to measure maternal behaviors and maternal/perinatal outcomes.

This project utilized a program evaluation design to measure the effectiveness of behavior changes (diet and exercise control) when a culturally sensitive intervention (*Comadre* sessions) was added to the standardized protocol. This type of design allowed the detection of change in behavior and clinical outcomes (Rouen, 2014).

Josepha Campinha-Bacote's cultural competence model (Campinha-Bacote, 2002) and Kurt Lewin's Model of Change (Lewin, 1951) were the supporting frameworks utilized to guide this project. Hispanic patients may find teaching interventions more acceptable if lessons about GDM are targeted in culturally focused ways. In order to set the foundation for a more culturally competent teaching intervention, the Campinha-Bacote's model supports the *Comadre* discussions by having the provider (FNP) consistently consider the five constructs of the model that connect the process of cultural competency to care delivery (Campinha-Bacote, 2002, p. 181). Using Kurt Lewin's Model of Change (Lewin, 1951), new or altered behaviors introduced by culturally sensitive discussions may be the impetus to improve perinatal outcomes in

Hispanic GDM; the benefit will be to both mother and baby, and to the provider (Campinha-Bacote, 2002).

Setting

This project took place at an outpatient clinic in Los Angeles County within the San Gabriel Valley region, located in Southern California. Two physicians and one FNP were the primary health care providers. The FNP (project lead) provided all *Comadre* discussion sessions. Three medical assistants worked with the provider to coordinate patient scheduling, taking height and weight, vital signs, and follow-up with referrals. Maternal and newborn outcomes were reported to the clinical site director on a monthly and quarterly basis.

Sample

The project goal was to enroll 20 Hispanic GDM mothers. Discussion meetings took place over three months. Demographics forms were part of the standard prenatal intake. Participants were limited to 20 women and were to be in groups of 4-6. The criteria for inclusion in this quality improvement project were limited to Hispanic women diagnosed with GDM according to the ACOG guidelines. Diagnostic criteria for GDM included two or more results of either a fasting blood sugar of $>95\text{mg/dL}$, one-hour blood sugar of $>180\text{ mg/dL}$, two-hour result of $>155\text{ mg/dL}$, and/or a three-hour result of $>140\text{ gm/dL}$ (Caughey & Turrentine, 2018). Once the diagnosis was confirmed, women with a first-time diagnosis of GDM and those with a previous GDM pregnancy were considered as candidates. Age inclusion was limited from 18-35; adolescents and women over 35 years were considered a high-risk population and were therefore excluded. Language criteria for participation included Spanish-only speakers and Spanish/English bilingual

participants. Exclusion criteria included any diagnosis of pre-eclampsia, placental disorders, cardiac disease, autoimmune disorders, sickle cell anemia, seizure disorders, substance abuse, viral and non-viral infections, and pre-existing DM. The rationale for exclusion is that any of the mentioned disorders may lead to hospitalization, early delivery or change in perinatal outcomes.

Ethical Issues

Approval for quality improvement project letter from clinic director was approved and obtained (Appendix A). The project began once IRB approval and patient consents (Appendix B) were obtained from California State University, Fullerton. An invitation via flyer (Appendix C) was posted in waiting areas and examination rooms. Participation was voluntary and anonymous.

Only aggregate data was collected in a confidential manner and stored in a secure locked cabinet by the Project Lead. Participation in *Comadre* sessions (date and time only) was noted in the individual patient's chart. A note stating that additional education regarding patient teaching/discussions regarding GDM, diet, and exercise was noted in the patient's progress note. Thus, any educational intervention regarding lifestyle behavior and to improve health is routinely documented in all patient's charts.

Planning the Quality Improvement Project

Stakeholders for this project included clinic obstetricians and the FNP. Group discussion sessions began once IRB approved the project to start. Project planning included the following:

Table 3

Timeline of Tasks

Semester	Goal (s)	Activities
Spring 2018		
April	prepare for IRB submission and approval of project Get director of clinic's letter of support for the QI project	CITI training Requested ORSP access to Grace Amaya
May	CSUF project approval	
June	Review and update TOE	Add more studies to TOE
July	Search for other applicable tools for GDM	Inquire regarding discussion groups
September	Get clinical director approval	Calculate trimesters participants are in to organize first group
Fall 2018		
October	IRB submission Prepare for teaching sessions	Start data review at office Flag possible candidates charts to plan enrollment Refine data collection tool, translate if required Consent approval and translate to Spanish Analyze data to confirm GDM diagnosis
December	Start implementing teaching sessions Once IRB approval	Book classroom for all classes at office Implement first session, Wednesday or Friday from 11:30 am or Saturdays at 12:30 pm
Spring 2019		
January	Continue discussion sessions	Communicate with analyst if any participants delivered
February- April	Analyze data Develop poster presentation	Communicate with analyst if any participants delivered
May	Complete written report and project dissemination presentation	

Methods of Evaluation**Group Discussion Guide**

The discussion guide consisted of eight questions (Appendix D & E). Questions 1-2 elicit information about emotions and motivation regarding GDM. Questions 3-5 elicit information about nutrition. Questions 6-7 elicit information about exercise.

Question 8 elicits information about personal emotions regarding their health during the GDM pregnancy. This discussion guide was utilized throughout the sessions as related to topic/session of the week. A total of three discussion sessions were implemented: Week one cover nutrition content, week two covered exercise and third week covered emotions and motivation (Appendix F). The three topics were not covered on the same day as the Sweet Success program. According to the CDAPP Sweet Success guidelines for care (2015), similar topics are covered at different intervals of their program. Their program covers these, and other educational topics related to GDM. All sessions were conducted in Spanish-only or in bilingual English/Spanish as indicated by group preference. Allowing the patients to reflect on discussions included open discussions between moderator and group members in a culturally appropriate approach. The set of questions were developed to an average of 3.5 grade level in back translation from English to Spanish as measured by the Flesch-Kincaid scale.

Discussion Sessions

Three *Comadre* groups of 3-4 participants were provided with 30 minutes of discussion sessions. All groups were referred to attend Sweet Success classes as part of the traditional obstetrical regimen. Comadres participants were concurrently attending both Sweet Success and *Comadre* sessions.

Data Analysis

Maternal and perinatal outcomes were compared between the 10 *Comadre* participants and 10 patients that participated in Sweet Success alone. Outcomes from existing patient records from both groups included intermittent maternal glucose levels and maternal weight levels. Newborn birth weight, type of delivery, and NICU

admissions were also considered but due to project time and length of pregnancy, this data will be obtained after delivery. The 10 Sweet Success patients were identified from the same practice using the same inclusion and exclusion criteria. Descriptive statistics and other applicable computations were utilized using the most current version of Pearson Education StatCrunch® and Microsoft Office Excel® spreadsheets.

FINDINGS

Sixteen women were identified with GDM diagnosis. Only ten ($n = 10$) met inclusion criteria and six were excluded due to either lack of transportation (2), childcare (1) or other secondary medical conditions as part of the exclusion criteria (3). Most women that met inclusion criteria were diagnosed at approximately 24-28 weeks of gestation or prior per ACOG guidelines (Caughey & Turrentine, 2018). Two of 10 participants were diagnosed using HgA1c. Final maternal and newborn outcomes will be completed upon delivery of all participants. Two groups were compared to summarize progress of future outcomes. Participants were divided into two groups and categorized as either as *Comadres* or the retrospective group non-participants ($n = 10$). Ongoing data collection includes maternal weight gain and blood sugar management.

Participants ages ranged from 18-35 (mean 27.2 [SD 6.2]) for the *Comadres* group (Table 4). Non-participant group ages ranged from 24-35 (mean 30.2 [SD 3.8]) years. Monitoring of weight gain from the start of prenatal care to current gestational weeks revealed range weight of 6 to 36 pounds with a mean weight gain of 14 pounds for the *Comadres* group compared to a weight gain range of minus 2 to 75 pounds with a mean weight gain of 24.3 pounds.

Preliminary findings in blood sugar maintenance were calculated to establish a difference between the two groups. At this point in time, there is insufficient evidence that the *Comadre* classes are affecting blood sugar maintenance (mean 106.4 mg/dL [SD 9.42] to mean 107.7 mg/dL [7.08]). Although the impact of blood glucose measures was not statistically significant, there was less weight gain in the *Comadres* group.

Table 4

Descriptive Statistics: Comadres and Non-Participants

	<i>Comadres</i>	Non-Participants
Age	M = 27.6, SD 6.2	M = 30.2, SD 3.8
Range Weight Gain	6 – 36 pounds	(-2) – 75 pounds
Mean Weight Gain	14 pounds*	24.3 pounds*
Blood Sugars Mean (SD)	106.4 mg/dL* (9.42)	107.7 mg/dL* (7.08)

*Not statistically significant, $p < 0.05$

Noteworthy findings for this quality improvement project include the qualitative comments from the *Comadre* discussions sessions. Methods of evaluation also included use of the Group Discussion Guide (Appendix D & E). Discussions lasted for approximately 30-45 minutes with each group who answered two to three open-ended questions per session about their experiences with diet, exercise, and emotions and motivation regarding GDM.

Many of the women expressed satisfaction from the attending the smaller group discussions as compared to the classroom setting prescribed by the CDAPP education. Some statements from participants included: “easier to ask questions”, “I get to learn from other mothers”, “change is hard”, “class helps me stay on track”, “this will help me keep my whole family healthy”. One of the women was noted to share healthy recipes using social media with the other women attending the *Comadre* sessions.

Practice providers noted interest and increased adherence to the GDM regimen by women attending the *Comadre* sessions. The provider requested consultation from the nurse to offer similar culturally competent methods of education to other high-risk

prenatal patients with chronic conditions such as hypertension and cardiovascular disease.

DISCUSSION

The state-recommended Diabetic Self-Management Education and Support (DSMES) program known as Sweet Success does not appear to meet the needs of the monolingual, Spanish-speaking, immigrant Hispanic woman with gestational diabetes (GDM). The purpose of the *Comadres* quality improvement project was to add a safe space in the outpatient primary setting for these women to have culturally and linguistically appropriate nurse/client discussions about their lived experience with GDM. In this chapter, the quantitative findings of weight gain and blood sugar control will be discussed, as well as the qualitative findings related to nutrition, exercise, and well-being. All findings will be compared to the literature and interconnected with the CCCT model.

Weight Gain

Although there was no statistical difference in pregnancy weight gain, the *Comadres* group had a mean weight gain of 14 pounds (range 6 to 36) compared to a mean weight gain of 24.3 pounds (range -2 to 75) for the non-participants group. Literature shows that excessive weight gain can lead to poor clinical outcomes in Hispanic mothers (Chasan-Taber, 2012; Goldstein et al., 2017; Landon et al., 2011), so even a moderate decrease in weight gain can have a positive outcome for the individual. The moderation in weight gain among the *Comadres* is in line with the ACOG recommended a pregnancy weight gain of 15-25 pounds for overweight women, and 11-20 pounds total weight gain for obese women (ACOG, 2013).

Weight management approaches such as appropriate types of food, meal preparation, and family support fall within the CCCT model. With each class session, questions from the group discussion guide elicited similar responses amongst the groups.

Most women agreed that the common issues they encountered within their families were associated with mixed meal preparation, social gatherings, fatigue, and economics of food acquisition. They shared obstacles that impeded the daily meal preparation necessary to maintain a healthy diet. Findings from this project showed better outcomes when the focus was on family bonding and working together rather than the goals of reducing blood sugar and weight management. Comments made by the participants included: “I have to cook what my husband and children like”, “I cannot afford to make two different meals,” “I am too tired to cook when I get home from work, it easier to go get fast food,” “My mother cooks for us, ” and “I want to eat healthy and teach my children to eat healthy”. Discussions increased self-awareness about the commonalities the women shared in facing barriers about dietary restrictions and they began to look at appropriate and reasonable management of their desire to eat healthy. Congruent with Lewin’s Change Theory, teaching their families to eat healthy was the driving force and the barriers described by the women were recognized as the opposing forces that impede change (Lewin, 1951). The nursing literature supports the comments about the perceived barriers of adjusting to dietary restrictions and the loneliness of feeling isolated during family meals (Carolan-Olah, Duarte-Gardea, Lechuga, & Salinas- Lopez, 2017; Laganá, 2003; Ramirez, Golash-Boza, Unger, & Baezconde-Garbanati, 2018). The component of Cultural Encounters from the CCCT model was supported by the aforementioned comments that were shared with the group and supports social behavior change. The facilitator was able to relate and understand the values, beliefs, and practices these women shared amongst the group. This relationship of mutual understanding helped build rapport within the group.

Blood Sugar Control

There was no difference in maintaining blood sugar levels within the ACOG parameters between the *Comadres* and the non-participant groups (mean 106.4 mg/dL [SD 9.42] to mean 107.7 mg/dL [SD7.08]). However, several studies support culturally competent interventions in managing blood sugars. The *Unidas* study reported support of mother/daughter dyads in helping to manage HgA1c and BMI to healthier levels than prior to the intervention (Sorkin et al., 2013). The *Centering Pregnancy Group Model* used Spanish language and culturally sensitive group teaching methods to encourage better control of blood sugars (Hieronymus, Combs & Gomez, 2015; Shellinger et al., 2017). *Dulce Mothers*, a peer educator group model supported findings of improved blood sugars (Phillis-Tsimikas et al., 2014). Positive findings may be related to university-based and/or non-profit funding which increased the length of studies and therefore presented better outcomes in laboratory and BMI findings, as compared to the short-term *Comadres* project.

Despite the lack of change in blood sugar results, the *Comadres* showed behavior change in tracking their blood sugars. Even with the tools and instructions from Sweet Success, three *Comadres* had not been monitoring their blood sugars nor had they turned in their blood sugar logs at their appointments. After the first session of the *Comadres* group, all participants turned in blood sugar logs at their next medical appointment. This was a notable behavior change identified by the front desk medical assistants and the health care providers. One receptionist stated, “We can’t believe it, first time turning in their logs.”

Qualitative Results

The role of the *Comadres* facilitator was to listen, connect, and promote understanding amongst the participants using the commonalities of culture: *personalismo* (personalism), *respeto* (respect), *familia* (family), and folk beliefs. Understanding the Hispanic woman's lived experience contributes to a partnership between the professional nurse educator and the women with GDM to engage in mutual learning. Comments revealed an openness to change and a willingness to learn more about controlling their GDM. A participant stated, "I am going to follow-up with my doctor after I have my baby to make sure my blood sugar is ok". Participants sought guidance on how to find inexpensive foods that fit the GDM diet. One participant stated, "I need to figure out foods that my family likes and are affordable". The *Comadres* discussions are consistent with the five themes identified by the research of Carolan-Olah et al. (2017) which are: (1) distress and fear; (2) realizing the changes required; (3) learning to manage GDM; (4) finding motivation; and (5) compliance despite limited understanding. The nurse facilitator initiated these very same themes by welcoming women to the group by acknowledging their steadfast commitment to the attendance of the discussions despite barriers and family responsibilities. Her welcoming words were "Gracias por asistir a estas clases por su bebé y su familia" (Thank you for attending these classes on behalf of your baby and your family). By doing so, the nurse was acknowledging the value of the family. The nurse facilitator noted that the body language and facial expressions of the participants revealed appreciation and bonding.

Small, intimate group discussions work better than one-to-one teaching sessions or large classroom lecture settings (Brown et al. 2015; Brown et al. 2018; Schellinger et

al., 2017). Hispanic women find that standardized diabetic education lacks connectedness (Sobel & Metzler Sarwin, 2016). The concept of connectedness was the central theme of Sobel & Metzler Sarwin's study describing culturally competent nurse-patient interactions. Crist's (2005) study described *Cafecitos* as a culturally safe and appropriate method of sharing health education, while at the same time benefitting from companionship, informal conversation, and the comfort of coffee and traditional Mexican pastries. The results of the Crist study described a trend towards increased participant knowledge about caregivers' use of home health assistance "they were better able to express their true attitudes to each other, including their hopes and doubts about family care" (Crist, 2005, p. 231). Throughout the course of the *Comadres* discussions, participants expressed an increased willingness to learn how to manage their GDM by navigating effectively between providers and clinic staff.

As Lewin theorized, social habits or customs impede changes in behavior and in order to change a social process must take place (Lewin, 1951). In Hispanic culture food is central to all celebrations and family gathering and it is considered rude to refuse the food offered. Many of the foods prepared for celebrations are not consistent with the GDM diet (Benavides-Vaello, & Brown, 2016; Ramírez, Golash-Boza, Unger, & Baezconde-Garbanati, 2018). Also, many Hispanic patients are of low socio-economic status, and foods that are high in sugar and carbohydrates are considerably more affordable than proteins, fruits, and vegetables (Benitez, Keller, Coe, & Tasevska, 2017).

With each progressive session, the CCCT framework encouraged provider/patient communication through self-efficacy. Patient activation is described in the medical literature as "one's ability to manage their health and health care" (Alegria, Sribney,

Perez, Laderman, & Keefe, 2009, p. S534). Patient activation parallels self-efficacy as described in the nursing and social science literature (Cardwell, 2013). Albert Bandura, the father of the social cognitive theory, was the first to address the nature and importance of self-efficacy in the determination of behavior. Bandura defined self-efficacy in his original social learning theory as “the conviction that one can successfully execute the behavior required to produce the [expected] outcomes” (Bandura,1977). Congruent with Lewin’s Change Theory, self-efficacy is important in the adoption of health-promoting behaviors and the elimination of health-impairing behaviors; it also influences decision-making and initiates and maintains the new healthy behaviors. Understanding the cultural underpinnings of Hispanic culture facilitates this process. Campinha-Bacote’s construct of cultural knowledge has the potential to guide providers to utilize the health beliefs that are beneficial and already available in the population of immigrant Hispanic women. When this project was initiated, it was thought that the *Comadre* discussions would lay the foundation to change (unfreeze) cultural behaviors and beliefs that can be a barrier to positive outcomes for GDM mothers and their babies. In reviewing the literature, it was discovered that the traditional dictates of Hispanic prenatal health practices are congruent with standard Western provider advice which are: “eat well/*come bien*, walk/*camina*, and don’t worry/*no se preocupe*” (Laganá, 2003, p. 120). The qualitative research findings from interviews in *The Mother Study*, an ethnographic study conducted between 1994 to 1996 in a small agricultural town of Watsonville, California, identified the influences of acculturation about pregnancy beliefs and practices. The 29 women interviewed shared their views about eating well, walking,

and avoiding stress which parallels the well-established U.S. medical protocol for GDM care which routinely focuses on nutrition, weight gain, and body image (Laganá, 2003).

Nutrition is related to *come bien* (eat well) and is a determinant of healthy birth outcomes. Immigrant women distrust processed or canned foods and are encouraged to eat homemade meals. More acculturated women reported that eating well was difficult. For immigrant women, the use of harmful substances and alcohol during pregnancy is criticized and leads to loss of respect and social power. Dieting during pregnancy was criticized. Women with a more Mexican cultural orientation reported that a fuller figure was seen by their spouse as ideal, as compared to more acculturated Mexican-American women who preferred to limit weight gain during pregnancy. Inadequate pre-pregnancy weight and inadequate weight gain contribute to low-birth-weight (Brown, et al, 2015; Brown et al., 2018; Ramirez et al, 2018).

Exercise from the Mexican perspective is seen as important for general well-being for pregnant women. Failure to maintain physical activity is a folk condition called *se pega* in which the fetus sticks to the inside of the uterus, making delivery difficult. Daily walks are encouraged. Immigrant women will give up more vigorous exercise such as aerobics or running as advised by the women in the family, even though their providers approve these exercises. Traditionally, certain physical activities such as lifting, bending, and standing long periods of time are discouraged by the family (Laganá, 2003). It is believed by the elder women of the family, especially grandmothers that these types of exercises will harm the baby (Benavides-Vaello & Brown, 2016; Kieffer, Willis, Arellano, & Guzman, 2002;).

The concept *preocuparse* is translated as the action of worrying and is similar to the U.S. concept of stress. The belief that worry will have a direct effect on the pregnancy and the developing fetus is a cultural dictate in the Hispanic culture. *No se preocupe* is enforced by the grandmothers through their power over the family. Pregnant women are to avoid anything that upsets or causes stress. It is an internalized decision by the pregnant woman not to respond to stressful outside influences. It places the responsibility back onto the pregnant woman in the form of expected health behavior of stress reduction. Family social support facilitates stress reduction. Women are encouraged to simplify their lives during pregnancy which may include leaving jobs and moving in with supportive family. The herb *manzanilla* (chamomile) is recognized for its calming effects and is frequently administered as a tea (Laganá, 2003).

Social Factors

Many social factors constitute barriers to health care adherence. These include language and literacy, perceived and actual discrimination, fear of deportation, and loneliness from being away from their country of origin and extended family.

English language proficiency in immigrant Hispanic patients is an impediment to safe communication between patient and provider (Parker et al., 2017). Proficiency in the Spanish language alone does not solve communication issues if cultural understanding is missing. In 2000, an exploratory study at San Francisco General Hospital demonstrated that language and culturally competent skills differ from only language proficiency (Fernandez et al., 2004). Effective cultural communication is becoming critical as the demographics of the U.S. are changing as Hispanics become the majority ethnic group by 2050 (United States Census Bureau, 2015).

Research demonstrates increased adherence to health care advice and better chronic care management when communication is improved between patient and provider. Patient trust is strengthened, and health disparities are reduced when patient and providers share ethnic backgrounds (Parker et al., 2017; Traylor et al., 2010). Limited English proficiency inhibits patient communication about their illness, question asking, and inquiries about care options. Inability to communicate effectively with a provider result in dissatisfaction, mistrust, and noncompliance with the health care system (Fernandez et al., 2011). Therefore, it was important that all materials (posters and hand-outs) be printed in Spanish and English. It was notable that during the *Comadre* discussions attention was centered towards information on the Spanish side of the written and printed materials.

Although some of the participants were fluent in English, they opted to participate in the Spanish group. Perhaps this dynamic stemmed from the concordance of the connectedness with the language and the culture; they shared their concerns and interests as future mothers with GDM. Patient engagement increased within the group because the discussions gave the women comfort in this closed social circle. Not only did the women share the language, but also their values were acknowledged by sharing common issues of living with their medical diagnosis and the nostalgia of cultural traditions that provided comfort.

Immigrant Hispanic women report incidents of perceived discrimination when seeking health care in the U.S. (Lara-Cinisomo, Girdler, Grewen, & Meltzer-Brody, 2016; Gaffney & McCormick, 2017). These topics came up in the *Comadres* discussions when the nurse facilitator discussed two questions from the discussion guide: “what is

hard about having diabetes?” and “what would you like to change?”. Loneliness and depression place these women at higher risk for psychosocial and physiological risk factors that may lead to postpartum depression for immigrant Hispanic pregnant women in the U.S. (Lara-Cinisomo et al., 2016).

Undocumented pregnant women seeking healthcare may be afraid to seek prenatal care until third trimester or at time of delivery because of fear of deportation (Goldfarb, Smith, Epstein, Burrows, & Wingate, 2016; Tobin, Di Napoli, & Tatano Beck, 2017). These political and legal conditions increase social isolation in women that migrate to the U.S. and leave their family, friends and sometimes their children behind. In their native country, women were free to walk in their neighborhoods or villages and socialize with neighbors and close families (Kieffer et al., 2002). Now, in the U.S. they disclose feeling unsafe to go out and walk in this unfamiliar environment and feel *encerrada* (closed-in) in their home (Gallardo, 2013; Goldschmidt & Colleta, 2016; Kieffer et al., 2002; Laganá, 2003).

Understanding gender roles as described in Hispanic culture is critical information for providers. *Marianismo* is the traditional gender role of the Hispanic woman; it restricts the woman to the home, as it is her place to stay home and tend to her role as a wife and mother (Lara-Cinisomo, Wood, & Fujimoto, 2018). The role of the husband can be a positive or negative factor in managing stress in these patients, as the husband is the primary and often sole provider for the family. Most Hispanic women that are pregnant in the U.S. rely on their spouse as the only social support system they to navigate in the new adapted society (Tobin, Di Napoli, & Tatano Beck, 2017). During pregnancy, women need increased social support to adapt to the role and expectations of motherhood. The

extended family is highly valued in Hispanic culture. The lack of extended family and missing familial support is an additional burden to the couple. According to one study, the family takes precedence over the individual, and this includes even the woman with GDM (Kieffer et al., 2002). Providers and agencies working with pregnant, immigrant women need to find ways to engage the partner in the women's health care routine, so that the couple can feel connected, and so the spouse is directly involved in a positive birth outcome for his family.

Several comments were shared amongst the groups that identified feelings of loneliness and powerlessness. Two of the young women shared with the *Comadres* group that they lived with their parents and did not have a spouse. Both expressed their concern about having to raise their babies alone. The eldest woman of that particular group stated and "at times it is best to be alone than with a man who dictates your life" (translated from Spanish).

Transportation is a critical issue, as many families have only one vehicle per household, and many Hispanic women are not encouraged or allowed to obtain a driver's license (Chasan-Taber, et al, 2010). The women in the *Comadres* group expressed these sentiments to the nurse facilitator: "I can't stay for the class today. I have no one to pick up my son from school." "My husband has to bring me because I don't drive, and he doesn't get out of work till 4:00."

Providers need to be sensitized to the nuances between Western culture and traditional cultural practices and beliefs that are health promoting and similar in benefit to the outcomes in women with GDM. Social behaviors should be deconstructed by providers in order for the provider to gain a better understanding of existent practices and

beliefs. This provides a foundation between patient and provider in order to understand the commonalities. This critical analysis of social behaviors is in accordance with Campinha-Bacote's constructs of self-awareness and the desire to provide transcultural patient interactions (Campinha-Bacote, 2002). This project provides awareness that it is the provider who needs to change, rather than the client because it is the provider's perception of the patient's cultural behaviors that are misconstrued (Lewin, 1951). The new collaborative paradigm will utilize the lived experience of the Hispanic woman with GDM to affect health outcomes for both mother and baby.

Summary

Although there was no statistically significant difference in either blood sugar values or weight gain between the two groups, there were promising shifts in mean weight gain and in behavior in the *Comadres*. Qualitative findings were more useful in identifying internal and external factors to change behaviors amongst participants. Discussion groups provided an opportunity to build rapport between patient and provider, as well as a platform for sharing the women's experience of managing the GDM recommendations despite cultural and economic barriers to standardized health care adherence.

Limitations

Generalization of this study is limited because of the sample size. Of the ten women in the *Comadres* group, only three women delivered by the time the study was presented. This made it difficult to measure outcomes. Recruitment of more participants was difficult due to scheduling conflicts, lack of transportation to/from the provider's office, and childcare issues. In addition, adherence to attendance at *Comadres* discussions

was hampered by participants' multiple appointments beyond prenatal care, including perinatology, ultrasounds, laboratory tests, Women, Infants and Children (WIC) Program, and Sweet Success classes.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This quality improvement project is a foundation to affect internal resistance for change and to initiate behaviors to mold new and healthier behaviors. Gestational Diabetes is an ongoing health problem in Hispanic women that requires better diet, exercise, and compliance of participants to the health care teams' recommendations. Findings of this quality improvement project revealed important qualitative support to suggest the implementation of the CCCT Model. In conclusion, organized intimate, culturally sensitive teaching programs promise a more effective way of connecting with high-risk pregnant Hispanic women. *Comadres* group sessions, with a culturally competent and bilingual provider, influenced motivation for change.

Recommendations

A few recommendations for future application of this culturally appropriate *Comadre* approach were identified. Providers should continue to follow *Comadre* participants through delivery and compare their outcomes to the women who participated in Sweet Success classes alone. Measures for the *Comadres* and the Sweet Success groups would include birth type, newborn weight, NICU admission, and Apgar scores (Appendix G).

It is recommended to maintain a *Comadres* approach due to positive acceptance by participants and providers. One method would be to include provider education about the cultural traditions of their patient population that might strengthen adherence to providers' medical recommendations

A major way that providers can remove barriers to participation would be synchronizing appointment schedules (i.e. labs, education, social services, etc.).

Participants and facilitator identified a need for small class sizes (three or four maximum) and increased time for further discussion. Conducting a formal satisfaction survey would provide invaluable information moving forward with the *Comadre* approach.

REFERENCES

- Albougami, A. S., Pounds, K. G., & Alotaibi, J. S. (2016). Comparison of four cultural competence models in transcultural nursing: A discussion paper. *International Archives of Nursing and Health Care*, 2(3), 1-5. doi: 10.23937/2469-5823/1510053
- Alegría, M., Sribney, W., Perez, D., Laderman, M., & Keefe, K. (2009). The role of patient activation on patient–provider communication and quality of care for US and foreign born Latino patients. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 24(3), 534-541. doi: 10.1007/s11606-009-1074-x
- American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. (2013). Weight gain during pregnancy. Committee opinion no. 548. *Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology*, 121(1), 210-212.
- American Diabetic Association (2016). *A1C*. Retrieved from www.diabetes.org/diabetes-basics/gestational/
- American Diabetes Association. (2018). 4. Lifestyle management: Standards of medical care in diabetes—2018. *Diabetes Care*, 41(Supplement 1), S38-S50. doi: 10.2337/dc18-S004
- American Heart Association. (2014). *Living healthy: Obesity information*. Retrieved from <http://www.heart.org>
- Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84(2), 191.

- Bellamy, L., Casas, J. P., Hingorani, A. D., & Williams, D. (2009). Type 2 diabetes mellitus after gestational diabetes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet*, *373*(9677), 1773-1779. doi: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(09\)60731-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(09)60731-5)
- Benavides-Vaello, S., & Brown, S. A. (2016). Sociocultural construction of food ways in low-income Mexican-American women with diabetes: A qualitative study. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, *25*(15-16), 2367-2377. doi: 10.1111/jocn.13291
- Benitez, T. J., Keller, C., Coe, K., & Tasevska, N. (2017). Investigation of the cultural context of sugars consumption behavior in low-income Mexican-American women. *Journal of Health Disparities Research and Practice*, *10*(2). Retrieved from <https://digitalscholarship.unlv.edu/jhdrp/vol10/iss2/6>
- Brown, S. A., García, A. A., Steinhardt, M. A., Guevara, H., Moore, C., Brown, A., & Winter, M. A. (2015). Culturally tailored diabetes prevention in the workplace: Focus group interviews with Hispanic employees. *The Diabetes Educator*, *41*(2), 175-183. doi: 10.1177/0145721714567233
- Brown, S. A., Perkison, W. B., García, A. A., Cuevas, H. E., Velasquez, M. M., Winter, M. A., & Hanis, C. L. (2018). The Starr county border health initiative: Focus groups on diabetes prevention in Mexican Americans. *The Diabetes Educator*, *XX*(X), 1-14. doi: 10.1177/0145721718770143.
- California Diabetes and Pregnancy Program (CDAPP) Sweet success resources and training center (2018). Retrieved from <http://www.cdappsweetsuccess.org>

- California Department of Public Health (2015). *California Diabetes and Pregnancy Program (CDAPP) Sweet Success Guidelines for Care*. Retrieved from cdappsweetsuccess.org
- Campinha-Bacote, J. (2002). The process of cultural competence in the delivery of healthcare services: A model of care. *Journal of Transcultural Nursing, 13*(3), 181-184. doi: 10.1177/10459602013003003
- Cardwell, M. S. (2013). Improving medical adherence in women with gestational diabetes through self-efficacy. *Clinical Diabetes, 31*(3), 110-115.
- Carolan-Olah, M., Duarte-Gardea, M., Lechuga, J., & Salinas-Lopez, S. (2017). The experience of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) among Hispanic women in a US border region. *Sexual & Reproductive Healthcare, 12*, 16-23.
- Caughey, A.B. & Turrentine, M. (2018). Gestational diabetes mellitus. Practice Bulletin No. 190. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. *Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology, 131*: e49-64.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2014). *National diabetes statistics report: Estimates of diabetes and its burden in the United States, 2014*. Retrieved from cdc.gov
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2015). *Diabetes Report Card, 2014*. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/diabetes/pdfs/library/diabetesreportcard2014.pdf>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2016). Overweight and obesity: Defining adult overweight and obesity. Retrieved from <https://www.cdc.gov/obesity/adult/defining.html>

- Chasan-Taber, L., Fortner, R. T., Gollenberg, A., Buonnaccorsi, J., Dole, N., & Markenson, G. (2010). A prospective cohort study of modifiable risk factors for gestational diabetes among Hispanic women: Design and baseline characteristics. *Journal of Women's Health, 19*(1), 117-124. doi: 10.1089/jwh.2009.1426
- Chasan-Taber, L. (2012). Physical activity and dietary behaviors associated with weight gain and impaired glucose tolerance among pregnant Latinas-. *Advances in Nutrition, 3*(1), 108-118. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3945/an.111.001214>
- Chen, Z., Watanabe, R. M., Stram, D. O., Buchanan, T. A., & Xiang, A. H. (2014). High calorie intake is associated with worsening insulin resistance and β -cell function in Hispanic women after gestational diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes Care, 37*(12), 3294-3300. doi: 10.2337/dc14-1433
- Chung, J. H., Voss, K. J., Caughey, A. B., Wing, D. A., Henderson, E. J. D., & Major, C. A. (2006). Role of patient education level in predicting macrosomia among women with gestational diabetes mellitus. *Journal of Perinatology, 26*(6), 328.
- Crist, J. D. (2005). Cafecitos and telenovelas: Culturally competent interventions to facilitate Mexican American families' decisions to use home care services. *Geriatric Nursing, 26*(4), 229-232. doi: 10.1016/j.gerinurse.2005.05.004
- Dabelea, D., Mayer-Davis, E. J., Lamichhane, A. P., D'agostino, R. B., Liese, A. D., Vehik, K. S., ... & Hamman, R. F. (2008). Association of intrauterine exposure to maternal diabetes and obesity with type 2 diabetes in youth. *Diabetes Care, 31*(7), 1422-1426.

- Duval, J. (2003). New programs for Hispanic women with breast cancer; comadre a comadre project. *New Mexico Woman*, 16(9) 15. Retrieved from <https://msmc.idm.oclc.org/login?url=https://search-proquestcom.msmc.idm.oclc.org/docview/229347121?accountid=12597>
- Fernandez, A., Schillinger, D., Warton, E. M., Adler, N., Moffet, H. H., Schenker, Y., ... & Karter, A. J. (2011). Language barriers, physician-patient language concordance, and glycemic control among insured Latinos with diabetes: The Diabetes Study of Northern California (DISTANCE). *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 26(2), 170-176. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11606-010-1507-6>
- Flegal, K. M., Carroll, M. D., Ogden, C. L., & Curtin, L. R. (2010). Prevalence and trends in obesity among US adults, 1999-2008. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 303(3), 235-241.
- Fung, G. P. G., Chan, L. M., Ho, Y. C., To, W. K., Chan, H. B., & Lao, T. T. (2014). Does gestational diabetes mellitus affect respiratory outcome in late-preterm infants? *Early Human Development*, 90(9), 527-530.
- Funnell, M. M., Brown, T. L., Childs, B. P., Haas, L. B., Hosey, G. M., Jensen, B., ... & Siminerio, L. M. (2009). National standards for diabetes self-management education. *Diabetes Care*, 32(Supplement 1), S87-S94.
- Gaffney, A., & McCormick, D. (2017). The Affordable Care Act: implications for health-care equity. *The Lancet*, 389(10077), 1442-1452. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(17)30786-9

- Gallardo, M. E. (2013). Context and culture: The initial clinical interview with the Latina/o client. *Journal of Contemporary Psychotherapy*, 43(1), 43-52. doi: 10.1077/s10879-012-9222-8
- Giacinto, R.E., Castaneda, S.F., Perez, R.L., Nodora, J.N., Gonzalez, P., Lopez, E.J., & Talavera, G.A. (2016). Diabetes cultural beliefs and traditional medicine use among health center patients in Oaxaca, Mexico. *Journal of Immigrant and Minority Health*, 18(6), 1413-1422. doi: 10.1007/s10903-015-0323-9
- Gill-Hopple, K. (2010). *Planning for the future: Making the second home through compadrazgo in Mexican American women* (Doctoral dissertation). Retrieved from ProQuest Dissertations Publishing. (3420652)
- Gobeil, O. (1973). El susto: A descriptive analysis. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 19(1-2), 38-43.
- Goldfarb, S. S., Smith, W., Epstein, A. E., Burrows, S., & Wingate, M. (2017). Disparities in prenatal care utilization among US versus foreign-born women with chronic conditions. *Journal of Immigrant and Minority Health*, 19(6), 1263-1270.
- Goldschmidt, V. J., & Colletta, B. (2016). The challenges of providing diabetes education in resource-limited settings to women with diabetes in pregnancy: Perspectives of an educator. *Diabetes Spectrum*, 29(2), 101-104. doi: 10.2337/diaspect.29.2.101
- Goldstein, R. F., Abell, S. K., Ranasinha, S., Misso, M., Boyle, J. A., Black, M. H., ... & Kim, Y. J. (2017). Association of gestational weight gain with maternal and infant outcomes: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 317(21), 2207-2225. doi: 10.1001/jama.2017.3635

- Hartling, L., Dryden, D. M., Guthrie, A., Muise, M., Vandermeer, B., Aktary, W. M., ... & Donovan, L. (2012). Screening and diagnosing gestational diabetes mellitus. *Evidence Report/Technology Assessment*, (210), 1.
- Hieronimus, L., Combs, L., & Gómez, M. (2015). Educational model in prenatal care to manage gestational diabetes mellitus in Spanish-speaking women. *AADE in Practice*, 3(6), 26-32. <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F2325160315603933>
- Homer, C. S., Ryan, C., Leap, N., Foureur, M., Teate, A., & Catling-Paull, C. J. (2012). Group versus conventional antenatal care for women. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 11(11). doi: 10.1002/14651858.CD007622.pub2
- Kieffer, E. C., Willis, S. K., Arellano, N., & Guzman, R. (2002). Perspectives of pregnant and postpartum Latino women on diabetes, physical activity, and health. *Health Education & Behavior*, 29(5), 542-556. doi:10.1177/10901980223702310
- Kilpatrick, S. J., Papile, L. A., & Macones, G. A. (2017). *Guidelines for perinatal care* (8th ed.). American Academy of Pediatrics. Washington, DC: Library of Congress Cataloging -in-Publication
- Kjos, S. L., Peters, R. K., Xiang, A., Henry, O. A., Montoro, M., & Buchanan, T. A. (1995). Predicting future diabetes in Latino women with gestational diabetes: Utility of early postpartum glucose tolerance testing. *Diabetes*, 44(5), 586-591.
- Koivusalo, S. B., Rönö, K., Klemetti, M. M., Roine, R. P., Lindström, J., Erkkola, M., ... & Andersson, S. (2016). Gestational diabetes mellitus can be prevented by lifestyle intervention: the Finnish Gestational Diabetes Prevention Study (RADIEL): A randomized controlled trial. *Diabetes Care*, 39(1), 24-30. doi: 10.2337/dc15-0511

- Komen, S. G. (2017). *Cafecitos breast cancer support group in Spanish*. Retrieved from <https://myoc3.org/cafecitos-breast-cancer-support-group-in-spanish-susan-g-komen-for-the-cure-oc-affiliate-1>
- Laganá, K. (2003). Come bien, camina y no se preocupe—Eat right, walk, and do not worry: Selective biculturalism during pregnancy in a Mexican American community. *Journal of Transcultural Nursing, 14*(2), 117-124. doi: 10.1177/1043659602250629
- Landon, M. B., Mele, L., Spong, C. Y., Carpenter, M. W., Ramin, S. M., Casey, B., ... & Sciscione, A. (2011). The relationship between maternal glycemia and perinatal outcome. *Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology, 117*(2 0 1), 218.
- Landon, M. B., & Nicholson, W. K. (2013). Gestational diabetes mellitus. Practice Bulletin No. 137. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. *Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology, (122)*, 406-16.
- Lara-Cinisomo, S., Girdler, S. S., Grewen, K., & Meltzer-Brody, S. (2016). A biopsychosocial conceptual framework of postpartum depression risk in immigrant and US-born Latina mothers in the United States. *Women's Health Issues, 26*(3), 336-343.
- Lara-Cinisomo, S., Wood, J., & Fujimoto, E. M. (2018). A systematic review of cultural orientation and perinatal depression in Latina women: are acculturation, Marianismo, and religiosity risks or protective factors? *Archives of Women's Mental Health, 1*-11.

- Lemley, M., & Spies, L. A. (2014, August 25). Traditional beliefs and practices among Mexican American immigrants with type II diabetes: A case study. *Journal of the American Association of Nurse Practitioners*, 27(4), 185-189. doi:
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/2327-6924.12157>
- Lewin, K. (1951). Field theory in social science. In D. Cartwright (Ed.), *Selected theoretical papers*. New York: Harper and Row.
- McCurley, J. L., Gutierrez, A. P., & Gallo, L. C. (2017). Diabetes prevention in US Hispanic adults: a systematic review of culturally tailored interventions. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 52(4), 519-529. doi:
10.1016/j.amepre.2016.10.028
- McKinney, E. S., James, S. R., Murray, S. S., Nelson, K., & Ashwill, J. (2017). *Maternal-child nursing (5th)*. St. Louis, MO: Elsevier Health Sciences.
- Metzger, B. E. (2007). Long-term outcomes in mothers diagnosed with gestational diabetes mellitus and their offspring. *Clinical Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 50(4), 972-979.
- Mocarski, M., & Savitz, D. A. (2012). Ethnic differences in the association between gestational diabetes and pregnancy outcome. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*, 16(2), 364-373.
- Moore, T. R., Griffing, G. T., Khardori, R., Talavera, F., Warshak, C. & Zurawin, R.K. (2018). Diabetes mellitus in pregnancy. Retrieved from
<https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/127547-overview#a2>

- Moyer, V. A. (2014). Screening for gestational diabetes mellitus: US preventive services task force recommendation statement. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, *160*(6), 414-420.
- Ogden, C. L., Carroll, M. D., Fryar, C. D., & Flegal, K. M. (2015). Prevalence of obesity among adults and youth: United States, 2011–2014. *NCHS Data Brief*, *219*(219), 1-8.
- Oza-Frank, R., Conrey, E., Bouchard, J., Shellhaas, C., & Weber, M. B. (2018). Healthcare experiences of low-income women with prior gestational diabetes. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*, 1-8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10995-018-2489-y>
- Palatnik, A., Mele, L., Landon, M. B., Reddy, U. M., Ramin, S. M., Carpenter, M. W., ... & Sciscione, A. (2015). Timing of treatment initiation for mild gestational diabetes mellitus and perinatal outcomes. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, *213*(4), 560-e1. doi: 10.1016/j.ajog.2015.06.022
- Parker, M. M., Fernández, A., Moffet, H. H., Grant, R. W., Torreblanca, A., & Karter, A. J. (2017). Association of patient-physician language concordance and glycemic control for limited-English proficiency Latinos with type 2 diabetes. *Journal of the American Medical Association, Internal Medicine*, *177*(3), 380-387.
- Philis-Tsimikas, A., Fortmann, A. L., Dharkar-Surber, S., Euyoque, J. A., Ruiz, M., Schultz, J., & Gallo, L. C. (2014). Dulce mothers: An intervention to reduce diabetes and cardiovascular risk in Latinas after gestational diabetes. *Translational Behavioral Medicine*, *4*(1), 18-25. doi: 10.1007/s13142-014-0253-4

- Rahman, M., & Berenson, A. B. (2010). Accuracy of current body mass index obesity classification for white, black and Hispanic reproductive-age women. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology, 115*(5), 982-988.
doi:10.1097/AOG.0b013e3181da9423.
- Ramírez, A. S., Golash-Boza, T., Unger, J. B., & Baezconde-Garbanati, L. (2018). Questioning the dietary acculturation paradox: a mixed-methods study of the relationship between food and ethnic identity in a group of Mexican-American women. *Journal of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics, 118*(3), 431-439.
- Rayle, A. D., Sand, J. K., Brucato, T., & Ortega, J. (2006). The “comadre” group approach: A wellness-based group model for monolingual Mexican women. *The Journal for Specialists in Group Work, 31*(1), 5-24. doi:
10.1080/01933920500341424
- Rouen, P. (2014). Aligning design, method, and evaluation with the clinical question. In K. Moran, R. Burson, & D. Conrad (Eds.), *The Doctor of Nursing practice scholarly project: A framework for success* (pp. 331-346). Burlington, MA: Jones & Bartlett.
- Rouse, D. J. (2014) Antepartum fetal surveillance. Practice Bulletin No. 145. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. *Obstetrics and Gynecology, 124*, 182-92.
- Russo, L. M., Nobles, C., Ertel, K. A., Chasan-Taber, L., & Whitcomb, B. W. (2015). Physical activity interventions in pregnancy and risk of gestational diabetes mellitus: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology, 125*(3), 576-582. doi: 10.1097/AOG.0000000000000691

- Saavedra, E. (2017). *Comadre a comadre*. Retrieved from <https://comadre.unm.edu/index.html>
- Sacks, D. A., Hadden, D. R., Maresh, M., Deerochanawong, C., Dyer, A. R., Metzger, B. E., ... & Persson, B. (2012). Frequency of gestational diabetes mellitus at collaborating centers based on IADPSG consensus panel–recommended criteria. *Diabetes Care*, 35(3), 526-528. doi: <https://dx.doi.org/10.2337%2Fdc11-1641>
- Schellinger, M. M., Abernathy, M. P., Amerman, B., May, C., Foxlow, L. A., Carter, A. L., ... & Rose, R. S. (2017). Improved outcomes for Hispanic women with gestational diabetes using the Centering Pregnancy© Group Prenatal Care Model. *Maternal and Child Health Journal*, 21(2), 297-305. doi: 10.1007/s10995-016-2114-x
- Shields, L., & Tsay, G.S. (2015). *California Diabetes and Pregnancy Program Sweet Success Guidelines for Care*. Retrieved from http://www.cdappsweetsuccess.org/Portals/0/2015Guidelines/2015__CDAPPSweetSuccessGuidelinesforCare.pdf
- Smedley, B. D., Stith, A. Y., & Nelson, A. R. (2003). Institute of Medicine, Board on Health Sciences Policy, Committee on Understanding and Eliminating Racial and Ethnic Disparities in Health Care. Unequal treatment: Confronting racial and ethnic disparities in health care. *Unequal treatment: confronting racial and ethnic disparities in health care [cited 2002 Mar 21]*. Retrieved from <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/fullerton/reader.action?docID=3378816&pg=196>

- Sobel, L. L., & Metzler Sawin, E. (2016). Guiding the process of culturally competent care with Hispanic patients: A grounded theory study. *Journal of Transcultural Nursing, 27*(3), 226-232. doi: 10.1177/1043659614558452
- Sorkin, D. H., Biegler, K. A., Peyreda, M., Kilgore, D., Dow, E., & Ngo-Metzger, Q. (2013). Unidas por la vida (United for life): Implementing a culturally-tailored, community-based, family-oriented lifestyle intervention. *Journal of Health Care for the Poor and Underserved, 24*(2), 116-138. doi: <https://doi-org.lib-proxy.fullerton.edu/10.1353/hpu.2013.0103>
- Sweeting, A. N., Ross, G. P., Hyett, J., Molyneaux, L., Constantino, M., Harding, A. J., & Wong, J. (2016). Gestational diabetes mellitus in early pregnancy: Evidence for poor pregnancy outcomes despite treatment. *Diabetes Care, 39*(1), 75-81. doi: 10.2337/dc15-0433
- Thorlby, R., Jorgensen, S., Ayanian, J.Z., & Sequist, T. (2011). Clinicians' views of an intervention to reduce racial disparities in diabetes outcomes. *Journal of the National Medical Association, 103*(9), 968-77. United States Census Bureau: American FactFinder (2015). Community facts. Retrieved from <https://factfinder.census.gov/faces/tableservices/jsf/pages/productview.xhtml?src=CF>
- Tobin, C. L., Di Napoli, P., & Beck, C. T. (2018). Refugee and immigrant women's experience of postpartum depression: a meta-synthesis. *Journal of Transcultural Nursing, 29*(1), 84-100. doi: 10.1177/1043659616686167

- Trudnak, T. E., Arboleda, E., Kirby, R. S., & Perrin, K. (2013). Outcomes of Latina women in Centering Pregnancy group prenatal care compared with individual prenatal care. *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health, 58*(4), 396-403. doi: 10.1111/jmwh.12000
- United States Census Bureau (2015). Retrieved from <https://www.census.gov/quickfacts/sangabrielcitycalifornia>
- Wong, T., Ross, G. P., Jalaludin, B. B., & Flack, J. R. (2013). The clinical significance of overt diabetes in pregnancy. *Diabetic Medicine, 30*(4), 468-474.
- Yee, L. M., Cheng, Y. W., Inturrisi, M., & Caughey, A. B. (2013). Gestational weight loss and perinatal outcomes in overweight and obese women subsequent to diagnosis of gestational diabetes mellitus. *Obesity, 21*(12), E770-E774. doi: 10.1002/oby.20490

APPENDIX A

CLINIC DIRECTOR APPROVAL

Raymond A. Barajas, M.D.
BOARD CERTIFIED IN OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

3560 SANTA ANITA AVENUE, SUITE H
EL MONTE, CA 91731
TELEPHONE: (626) 579-9595
FAX: (626) 579-3851

DATE: August 19, 2018

TO: Noemi Barajas, CSUF Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Student

FROM: R.A. Barajas, M.D., F.A.C.O.G., Clinic Director

RE: DNP Project Implementation and Clinical Data

This memorandum confirms my permission to implement *Comadres Discussion Sessions* into the prenatal care offered at Dr. Barajas, MD, Inc. I understand these group discussions will provide additional patient teaching and support. These sessions will be documented in the patients' chart as culturally appropriate discussions regarding diet and exercise, and how the diagnosis of gestational diabetes affects their lifestyle. Any educational intervention regarding lifestyle behavior to improve patients' health is routinely documented in all patient charts. A simple discussion guide will be used to allow open discussion for Hispanic gestational diabetics during the sessions.

I also approve the use of clinical data that is reported to our clinic from a local contracted large institution. Patient data include delivery dates, delivery type, newborn weight in grams, maternal diagnosis during pregnancy, and ethnicity. No patient identifiers will be used for the project. This clinical facility will remain as an anonymous institution for the protection of our patients and the community we serve.

Should you have any further questions, feel free to contact at 626.579.9595 or Rbmd UCLA@aol.com

Raymond Barajas M.D. FACOG
Clinic Director

APPENDIX B

CONSENTS

California State University Fullerton Research Study Consent Form
--

Study Title: Comadre Discussions: A Culturally Sensitive Intervention to Improve Gestational

Diabetes Outcomes in Hispanic Women

Protocol Number: HSR-18-19-361

Researchers: *Noemi Barajas*, MSN, FNP, RNC-MNN, CSUF School of Nursing

Maria Matza, PhD, RN, CNS, PHN, Associate Professor, CSUF School of

Nursing

Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN, Professor

Coordinator, CSUF Graduate Nursing

Program, Director, Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

You are being asked to take part in a project carried out by Noemi Barajas. This consent form explains the project study and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

Purpose. Gestational diabetes is responsible for poor maternal and fetal outcomes. This project will compare perinatal outcomes including intermittent maternal sugar levels, mothers' weight levels, newborn birth weight, type of delivery, and newborn's admission after birth in Hispanic women diagnosed with diabetes in pregnancy between those participating culturally sensitive discussion sessions (Comadre Discussions) as a support to the California standard prenatal gestational diabetes educational program, Sweet Success and those who only participated in the standard prenatal gestational diabetes educational program.

Participants will attend three discussion meetings, each lasting about 30 minutes per session. The three meetings will take place over a period of three months.

You cannot take part in this study if you are under 18, or over 35 years old. Any medical diagnosis of pre-eclampsia, placental disorders, cardiac disease, autoimmune disorders, sickle cell anemia, seizure disorders, substance abuse, viral and non-viral infections, and pre-existing diabetes. The rationale for exclusion is that any of these disorders may lead to hospitalization, early delivery or change in mother and newborn outcomes.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you take part in the study, you will be asked to attend three group discussions sessions. Complete description of project includes:

- The principal investigator, who is a bilingual and bicultural registered nurse trained in diabetes education, will conduct the *Comadre* groups.
- Participants will be limited to 20 women and will be in groups of 4-6.
- Four *Comadre* groups of 4-6 participants will be provided with 30 minutes discussion sessions.
- *Comadres* participants will be concurrently attending both Sweet Success and *Comadre* sessions.
- Each session will focus on three topics by using a discussion guide with eight simple questions regarding nutrition, exercise and personal emotions regarding your health during your pregnancy with gestational diabetes.
 - Handouts on the topic of the class are available in both English and Spanish.
- The three-group discussions will spread out and take place over three months period.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

The potential benefits to you for taking part in this study are: The guided group discussions regarding gestational diabetes may allow pregnant women to gain a better understanding of diet, exercise and stress during pregnancy. These factors may contribute to a healthier pregnancy and infant. The potential societal benefit of the project may be measured in healthy outcomes for mother and baby. Additionally, if you take part in this study you may help other gestational diabetic pregnant women in the future.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

This protocol contains no foreseeable risks.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

Confidentiality will be provided to the extent allowed by law. Complete data collection used in this study will be protected and stored in a locked private office and destroyed three years after completion of project. Data will be stored in a locked cabinet, coded to a master list with master list kept separate from data, and password protected computer. The results of this study may be published or presented at professional meetings, but the identities of all research participants will remain anonymous.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?**There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study.**

You will not receive money or any other form of compensation for taking part in this study.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Noemi Barajas, at (323) 333-4514 or nbarajas16@csu.fullerton.edu.

If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719, or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

What does my signature on this consent form mean?

Your signature on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
- You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns
- You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or I have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By signing below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You will be given a copy of this signed and dated consent form to keep.

Name of Participant (please print) _____

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

Universidad Estatal de California Fullerton
--

Formulario de consentimiento para estudios de investigación

Título del estudio: Discusiones entre Comadres: Una Intervención Culturalmente Sensible para Mejorar los Resultados de la Diabetes Gestacional en las Mujeres Hispánicas

Número de protocolo: HSR-18-19-361

Investigadores: *Noemi Barajas*, MSN, FNP, RNC-MNN, CSUF Escuela de Enfermería

Maria Matza, PhD, RN, CNS, PHN, Profesora Asociada, CSUF Escuela de Enfermería

Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN, Profesora

Coordinator, CSUF Enfermería de Posgrado

Directora de Programa, Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

Se le pide participar en un proyecto llevada a cabo por Noemi Barajas. Este consentimiento formulario explica el proyecto estudio y su parte en ella Si decides unirte al estudio. Este consentimiento el formulario explica el proyecto estudio y su parte en ella Si decides unirte al estudio. Por favor, lea el formulario cuidadosamente, tomando todo el tiempo que necesite. Pídale a la investigadora que le explique cualquier cosa que no entienda. Usted puede decidir no unirse al estudio. Si se une al estudio, puede cambiar de opinión más tarde y dejar el estudio en cualquier momento. No habrá penalidad o pérdida de servicios o beneficios si decide no tomar parte en el estudio.

¿De qué se trata este estudio?

Propósito. La diabetes gestacional es responsable de los resultados pobres maternos y fetales. Este proyecto comparará los resultados perinatales incluyendo los niveles de azúcar materna intermitente, los niveles de peso de la mamá, el peso del recién nacido, el tipo de parto y la admisión del recién nacido después del nacimiento en mujeres hispanas diagnosticadas con diabetes durante el embarazo entre Ésas participantes en sesiones de discusión culturalmente sensibles (discusiones de Comadre) como un apoyo al programa de educación prenatal estándar de California para la diabetes gestacional, el éxito dulce y aquellos que sólo participaron en la gestación prenatal estándar programa educativo de diabetes.

Los participantes asistirán a tres reuniones de discusión, cada una dura unos 30 minutos por sesión. Las tres reuniones se llevarán a cabo en un periodo de tres meses.

No puede participar en este estudio si usted es menor de 18 años, o tiene más de 35 años. Cualquier diagnóstico médico de preeclamsia, desordenes de placenta, enfermedades cardíacas, desordenes autoinmunes, anemia de glóbulos falciformes, desordenes convulsivos, abuso de sustancias, infecciones virales y no virales, y diabetes preexistente. La razón fundamental para la exclusión es que cualquiera de estos desordenes puede llevar a la hospitalización, el parto prematuro o el cambio en los resultados de la madre y del recién nacido.

¿Qué se me pedirá que haga si estoy en este estudio?

Si usted participa en el estudio, se le pedirá que asista a tres sesiones de grupos de discusión. La descripción completa del proyecto incluye:

- El investigador principal, que es una enfermera registrada bilingüe y bicultural entrenada en la educación de la diabetes, conducirá los grupos de *Comadre*.
- Las participantes estarán limitados a 20 mujeres y estarán en grupos de 4-6.
- Cuatro grupos de *Comadre* de 4-6 participantes serán proporcionados con 30 minutos de sesiones de discusión.
- Las participantes de comadres participarán simultáneamente en las sesiones de dulce éxito (Sweet Success) y *comadre*.
- Cada sesión se centrará en tres temas utilizando una guía de discusión con ocho preguntas sencillas sobre nutrición, ejercicio y emociones personales con respecto a su salud durante su embarazo con diabetes gestacional.
 - Folletos sobre cada tema de la clase están disponibles en inglés y español.
- La discusión de tres-grupos se extenderá y tendrá lugar durante un período de tres meses.

¿Hay algún beneficio para mí si estoy en este estudio?

Los beneficios potenciales para usted para participar en este estudio son: Las discusiones de grupos guiados con respecto a la diabetes gestacional pueden permitir a las mujeres embarazadas obtener una mejor comprensión de la dieta, el ejercicio y el estrés durante el embarazo. Estos factores pueden contribuir a un embarazo y a un niño más sano. El beneficio potencial de la sociedad del proyecto puede medirse en resultados saludables para la madre y el bebé. Además, si usted participa en este estudio usted puede ayudar a otras mujeres embarazadas diabéticas gestacionales en el futuro.

¿Hay algún riesgo para mí si estoy en este estudio?

Este protocolo no contiene riesgos previsible.

¿Se mantendrá mi información anónimo o confidencial?

La confidencialidad se proporcionará en la medida permitida por la ley. La recopilación completa de datos utilizada en este estudio será protegida y almacenada en una oficina privada bloqueada y destruida tres años después de la terminación del proyecto. Los resultados de este estudio pueden ser publicados o presentados en reuniones

profesionales, pero las identidades de todos los participantes de la investigación permanecerán anónimas.

¿Hay algún costo o pago por estar en este estudio?

No habrá costos para usted por participar en este estudio.

Usted no recibirá dinero ni ninguna otra forma de compensación por participar en este estudio.

¿Con quién puedo hablar si tengo preguntas?

Si tiene alguna pregunta acerca de este estudio o de la información de este formulario, por favor comuníquese con el investigador Noemi Barajas, al (323) 333-4514 o nbarajas16@csu.fullerton.edu.

Si usted tiene preguntas sobre sus derechos como participante de la investigación, o le gustaría reportar una inquietud o queja acerca de este estudio, por favor comuníquese con la Junta de revisión institucional al (657) 278-7719, o correo electrónico IRB@fullerton.edu

¿Cuáles son mis derechos como voluntario de estudio de investigación?

Su participación en este estudio de investigación es totalmente voluntaria. Usted puede optar por no ser parte de este estudio. No habrá penalidad para usted si decide no participar. Usted puede optar por no responder a preguntas específicas o para dejar de participar en cualquier momento.

¿Qué significa mi firma en este formulario de consentimiento?

Su firma en este formulario significa que:

- Usted entiende la información que se le da en este formulario
- Usted ha sido capaz de hacer preguntas a los investigadores y de indicar cualquier preocupación
- La investigadora ha respondido a sus preguntas y preocupaciones
- Usted cree que entiende el estudio de investigación y los beneficios y riesgos potenciales que están involucrados.

Declaración de consentimiento

He leído cuidadosamente y/o he tenido los términos utilizados en este formulario de consentimiento y su significado se me explicó. Al firmar a continuación, estoy de acuerdo que tengo por lo menos 18 años y estoy de acuerdo en participar en este proyecto. Se le dará una copia de este formulario de consentimiento firmado y fechado para conservarlo.

Nombre del Participante (por favor imprima) _____

Firma de la Participante _____ Fecha _____

Firma de la Investigadora _____ Fecha _____

APPENDIX C

COMMUNITY ANNOUNCEMENT (FLYER)

Comadre Project

What is this? Friendly conversation and education for women with gestational diabetes

When? Tuesdays, Wednesdays and Fridays

Time: With Arrangements or appointment

Where?

At your doctors clinic

**Call Noemi at (323) 333-4514
for more information and to join a group**

Cost: Free

All classes are bilingual (Spanish and English)

**Got
diabetes??**

Proyecto Comadre

¿Qué es? Pláticas y educación para las mujeres con diabetes gestacional

¿Cuándo? Martes, Miércoles y Viernes

¿A qué hora? Con arreglos o cita

¿Dónde?

En la clínica de su médico

**Llame a Noemí (323) 333-4514
para más información y unirse a un grupo**

Costo: Gratis

Las pláticas son bilingües (en Inglés y español)

**¿¿Tienes
diabetes??**

APPENDIX D

DISCUSSION GUIDE QUESTIONS (ENGLISH)

Group Discussion Guide

These questions about diabetes during pregnancy will be used to facilitate discussion. After participants answer the questions, the nurse facilitator will provide clarifying information to participants.

1. What is hard about having diabetes?
2. What would you like to change?
3. What do you think are healthy foods?
4. What keeps you from eating healthy foods?
5. What makes you want to eat healthy food?
6. What stops you from exercising?
7. What makes you want to exercise?
8. Why do you want to stay healthy?

3.5 average Flesch-Kincaid Score

APPENDIX E**DISCUSSION GUIDE QUESTIONS (SPANISH)****Guía de Discusiones de Grupo**

Estas preguntas sobre la diabetes durante el embarazo se utilizarán para facilitar la discusión. Después de que las participantes respondan las preguntas, la enfermera facilitadora de la compartirá clarificación de la información a las participantes.

1. ¿Qué es lo más difícil de tener diabetes?
2. ¿Qué le gustaría cambiar?
3. ¿Cuáles cree usted son los alimentos más saludables?
4. ¿Qué le impide comer alimentos saludables?
5. ¿Qué le hace comer alimentos saludables?
6. ¿Qué le impide hacer ejercicio?
7. ¿Qué le hace querer hacer ejercicio?
8. ¿Por qué quiere mantenerse sana?

Puntaje promedio de Flesch-Kincaid

APPENDIX F

SAMPLE OF CLASS HANDOUTS

Week 1: The Importance of Diet During your Pregnancy

- Maintaining good blood sugar
- Inappropriate weight gain
- Setting your weight goals
- Understanding carbohydrates
- Understanding fats
- Food likes and dislikes
- Usual meal preparations for the family
- Access and affordability of food

Week 2: The Importance of Exercise During your Pregnancy

- Plan for your exercise
- 20-30 minutes per day, most days of the week unless contraindicated with the pregnancy
- Moderate-intensity physical activity
- Choose location that works for you
- Walking helps burn calories
- Exercise with your family
- Walk your children to school
- Family walks
- Use a stroller to walk with your baby

Week 3: Emotions and Motivation with Your Pregnancy

We don't know what causes gestational diabetes, but we have some clues. The placenta supports the baby as it grows. Hormones from the placenta help the baby develop. But these hormones also block the action of the mother's insulin in her body. This problem is called insulin resistance. Insulin resistance makes it hard for the mother's body to use insulin. She may need up to three times as much insulin.

Gestational diabetes starts when your body is not able to make and use all the insulin it needs for pregnancy. Without enough insulin, glucose cannot leave the blood and be changed to energy. Glucose builds up in the blood to high levels. This is called hyperglycemia. (ADA, 2018)

Semana 1: La Importancia de la Dieta Durante su Embarazo

- Mantener el buen azúcar en la sangre
- Ganancia de peso inadecuada
- Ajuste de sus objetivos de peso
- Entender los carbohidratos
- Entender las grasas
- La comida que le gusta y no le gusta
- Comidas típicas que prepara para la familia
- Alimentos accesibles y económicos

Semana 2: La Importancia del Ejercicio Durante su Embarazo

- Planea su ejercicio
- 20-30 minutos por día, la mayoría de los días de la semana a menos que esté contraindicado con el embarazo
- Actividad física de intensidad moderada
- Elija la ubicación que funciona para usted
- Caminar ayuda a quemar calorías
- Haga ejercicio con su familia
- Camine a sus hijos a la escuela
- Paseos en familia
- Use un cochecito para caminar con su bebé

Semana 3: Emociones y Motivación con su Embarazo

No sabemos qué causa la diabetes gestacional, pero tenemos algunas ideas. La placenta apoya al bebé cuando crece. Las hormonas de la placenta ayudan al bebé a desarrollarse. Pero estas hormonas también bloquean la acción de la insulina de la madre en su cuerpo. Este problema se llama resistencia a la insulina. Resistencia a la insulina hace que sea difícil para el cuerpo de la madre para usar la insulina. Ella puede necesitar hasta tres veces más insulina.

La diabetes gestacional comienza cuando su cuerpo no es capaz de hacer y utilizar toda la insulina que necesita para el embarazo. Sin suficiente insulina, la glucosa no puede dejar la sangre y se cambiará a energía. La glucosa se acumula en la sangre a niveles altos. Esto se llama hiperglucemia. (ADA, 2018)

APPENDIX G
BIRTH OUTCOMES

	<i>Comadres</i> (6 delivered)	Sweet Success Participants (10 delivered)
Delivery type		
Spontaneous Vaginal	<i>n</i> = 2	<i>n</i> = 3
Vacuum	<i>n</i> = 0	<i>n</i> = 1
Forceps	<i>n</i> = 0	<i>n</i> = 0
Primary Cesarean Section	<i>n</i> = 2	<i>n</i> = 3
Repeat Cesarean Section	<i>n</i> = 2	<i>n</i> = 3
Live Birth	<i>n</i> = 6 (100%)	<i>n</i> = 10 (100%)
Neonatal Outcomes		
Jaundice	<i>n</i> = 0	<i>n</i> = 1 (10%)
Macrosomia	<i>n</i> = 0	<i>n</i> = 1 (10%)
Hypoglycemia	<i>n</i> = 0	<i>n</i> = 3 (30%)
NICU Admission	<i>n</i> = 0	<i>n</i> = 1 (10%)
Apgar Scores		
8-10	<i>n</i> = 6 (100%)	<i>n</i> = 8 (80%)
5-7	<i>n</i> = 0	<i>n</i> = 2 (20%)
<5	<i>n</i> = 0	<i>n</i> = 0

Note: Chart reflects 16 patients that have delivered. Four patients (4 *Comadres*) were still pregnant at the completion of the project.

APPENDIX H
TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Table 1.GDM Overview

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusion/Study Limitations
Investigate obesity trends and incidence of overweight and obesity among US adults. (Flegal, Carroll, Ogden, & Curtin, 2010)	Stratified, multistage probability cluster	1999-2008	BMI measurements for overweight was 25.0-29.9	1999-2000 Median Men, ages 20-39, BMI = 26.0%	Incidence of obesity in US continues to exceed 30% with most age groups and gender.
		5555 adult men & women, ages < 20 from NHANES	BMI measurement for obesity was ≥ 30.0	BMI for overweight & obesity combined male & female were 68.0%	
		Hyattsville, MD	999-2008 obesity trends	32.2% males 35.5% females	
			2007-2008 obesity & overweight incidence		
Assess clinicians of an intervention to decrease health disparities among DM outcomes (Thorlby, Jorgensen, Ayanian, & Sequist, 2011)	Qualitative Semi-structured interviews	12 doctors	Clinicians barriers	Most clinicians (13/17) agreed presence of racial disparities with DM management; 4/17 did not agree.	Clinicians identified disparities in providing care
		5 NPs	Drug copayments, visit copayments, lack of access to good food & exercise, & diet		
	Racial disparities, clinicians' attitudes, diabetes management	Eastern Massachusetts			Thematic analysis agreed to focus on culturally tailored patient dietary guidance interventions

					instead socioeconomic issues
Investigate wt. loss and associated perinatal outcomes with GDM in overweight & obese women. (Yee et al, 2013)	Retrospective cohort study Variables: IV-wt. loss once diagnosed with GDM DV-perinatal outcomes	2001-2004 26,205 overweight & obese GDM women enrolled in Sweet Success Multiple community & institutions centers in California Latina (N = 15,874) highest population for study	Weight change - difference between first Sweet Success visit & last visit. Perinatal outcomes: Gestational weight, type of delivery, NICU admissions & antepartum admissions	Third trimester wt. loss was related to some improved neonatal and maternal outcomes. Only 1,367 (5.2%) lost some wt. in 3 rd trimester; Mean weight loss 4.3 pounds. Enrollment mean gestational age was 26.8 wks (median 29.5). Last visit means of 34.8 wks (median 8.9) Among women who lost weight with adverse perinatal outcomes associated with wt. loss were: Intra-uterine fetal demise (aOR 1.77, 95% CI 0.77-4.07) Preterm deliveries < 34 wks increased (aOR 1.71, 95% CI 1.23-2.37), and SGA aOR 1.69, 95% CI 1.32-2.17)	GDM is usually found in 3 rd trimester, once dx. they are referred to Sweet Success. Wt. loss in trimester may indicate poor controlled GDM
Assessing for macrosomia risks in GDM women by	Retrospective study Variables:	2001-2002 9,182 women	Demographics: Parity, ethnicity, maternal wt., preferred language,	Compared to College-educated women, High school & middle school = 21% (RR), & 35%	Lower level of education had an increased rate of macrosomia

<p>considering maternal educational level. (Chung et al., 2006)</p>	<p>Multivariable model included level of education, ethnicity, parity, language preferred, post-gestation & mother's wt.</p>	<p>GDM Women referred to Sweet Success Program Long Beach, California</p>	<p>GA, Newborn weight, type of delivery, & NICU admission Years of education Macrosomia = NBW > 4000 grams</p>	<p>(RR)... women with high school education had 21% relative risk of macrosomia and those with middle school education had 35% relative risk Latina women reported highest education for middle school, second high school, third college, and fourth not reported. None English-speaking Latinas were 12% more likely to deliver a macrosomic baby compared to Caucasian women</p>	<p>14.1% did not report their education level, missing data Adherence to treatment by questioning educational level versus biological or lifestyle differences</p>
<p>Determine prevalence, perinatal outcomes, & clinical characteristics of GDM when identified at < 24 wks vs. > 24 wks of gestation. (Sweeting et al., 2016)</p>	<p>Multiethnic cohort study. Variables: Maternal characteristics, clinical outcomes (maternal, neonatal)</p>	<p>1991-2011. 4,873 women Stratified by pre-existing DM, & GDM gestational age: < 12 wks (n = 68) 12-23 wks (1,247), ≥ 24 wks (3,493) Antenatal diabetes clinic Australia</p>	<p>Maternal tx. by type of DM and timing of GDM diagnosis Maternal outcomes: Hypertensive disorders, Cesarean Section, neonatal jaundice, preterm deliveries, Neonatal outcomes: Macrosomia, LGA, & NICU admissions</p>	<p>Women in study were more on Southeast Asian and Anglo-Celtic background. No Hispanics Hypertensive disorders, Cesarean Section, neonatal jaundice, preterm deliveries greater with pre-existing diabetes followed by < 12 wks, and last > 24 ($P < 0.0001$) GDM diagnosed at < 12 wks compared to pre-existing T2DM: Macrosomia (21.8% vs. 20.3%, $P=0.8$), LGA (39.6% vs. 32.8%, $P=0.4$),</p>	<p>Regardless early dx and/or tx. of GDM, result in poor outcomes that are comparable to those of women with pre-existing DM Early GDM group were preselected as high-risk due to poor neonatal outcomes in stillbirths Poor control on outcomes and many lost for follow-up after delivery</p>

				& NICU admissions (38.5% vs. 39.7%, $P=0.9$). Conclusion was that GDM has equivalent neonatal outcomes to preexisting diabetes	
To assess modifiable risk factors such as physical activity and stress from GDM Hispanic women in early pregnancy (Chasan-Taber et al., 2010)	Prospective cohort study Proyecto Buena Salud Variables: physical activity, trait anxiety, perceived stress & depressive symptoms	2006-2008 N = 632 GDM Hispanic women, predominately Puerto Rican & Dominican Republican descent Ambulatory obstetrical practices Amherst, MA	Validated questionnaires: Physical activity, modified version of Pregnancy Physical Activity Questionnaire (PPAQ) Psychosocial stress, Chohen's Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-14) Anxiety, Spielberger State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) Depression, Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS)	69% < 24 years 87% unmarried 48% < high school education 5.2% met physical activity during pregnancy Stress (mean 26.9 ± 7.1) Anxiety (mean 41.6 ± 10.4) Depression symptoms (33.2%) High acculturation women less likely to live with partner versus low acculturation women (OR: 0.6, 95% CI 0.4-0.8)	Findings will help health care providers to plan intervention programs to tackle GDM risk factors. 40% reported use of alcohol prior to pregnancy, decreased to 3% with pregnancy 50% used tobacco prior to pregnancy, decreased to 15% in early pregnancy

Notes. wks = weeks; DM = diabetes mellitus; GDM = gestational diabetes mellitus; tx. = treatment; LGA = large for gestational age; NICU = neonatal intensive care unit; BS = blood sugar; IV = independent variable; DV = dependent variable; SGA = small for gestational age; NHANES = national health and nutrition examination survey; NPs = nurse practitioners

Table 2. Standard Educational Programs for GDM

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Conclusion/Study Limitations
Synthesize current studies of GDM and physical activity (Russo et al., 2015)	Meta-analysis of RCT's studies	2010-2014 Stratified 10 studies met inclusion criteria <i>n</i> = 3,401 6-22 weeks GA Various countries: Three in Spain, two in U.S., one in Australia, Croatia, Denmark, The Netherlands, & Norway.	Inclusion criteria included RCT's, pregnant women without GDM at baseline, BMI, exercise, GA, & incidence of GDM Conveyed RCTs of physical activity interventions of effects of physical activity-only for at risk patients of GDM.	28% lower risk (95% CI 9-42%) in intervention group (physical activity) compared to control group (RR 0.72, <i>p</i> = .005) Heterogeneity was low (<i>p</i> = .33) Exercise provides minor protection in developing GDM 8 of 10 studies used group exercise models	Evaluation type, duration, timing, & compliance activity regimens necessary advised by obstetrical guidelines Only two studies were done in the U.S.
Investigate the experience of GDM women of Mexican descent (Carolan-Olah, Duarte-Gardea, Lechuga & Salinas-Lopez, 2017)	Qualitative	2016 GDM Hispanic women of Mexican descent <i>n</i> = 18 El Paso, TX	6 semi-structured face-to-face questions in Spanish or English language Descriptive characteristics included age, yrs of education, marital status, & health insurance	5 themes transpired from analysis: Distress & fear, realizing the changes required, learning to manage GDM, finding motivation, & compliance despite limited understanding 15/18 agreed with distress & fear when dx with GDM 12/18 could not make sense of dx. 14/18 agreed to eating large meals & restricted food	Highly motivated participants from interest of their baby to change diet & exercise with GDM Low literacy information of food values noted Participants struggled with learning and adjustment to dx. Literature review discussed Marianismo

16/18 explained taking BS
was very difficult

14/18 established strategies to
hunger & self-management

Notes. DM = diabetes mellitus; GDM = gestational diabetes mellitus; PT's = patients, RCT =Randomize controlled trials; DPP = diabetes prevention program; B/P = blood pressure; BMI = body mass index; IV = independent variable; DV = dependent variable; YRS = years; WT = weight; WKS = weeks; GA = gestational age

Table 3. Health Beliefs of Pregnant Hispanics

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Conclusion/Study Limitations
Culturally competent intervention (<i>Unidas</i>) using mother-daughter relationship for low-income Mexican-American with DM and obesity (Sorkin et al., 2013)	Randomized, 2 group pilot study Variables: IV- Unidas por la Vida Intervention Group DV-DPP	N = 185 paired mother-daughter Latinas \geq 18 yrs, living within 25 miles of mother & BMI \geq 25 Santa Ana, CA	Baseline questionnaire of demographics Medical & other data- B/P, BMI, & some biomedical data Satisfaction survey	Demographics- 60% of paired participants had no insurance, 74% lived together with very low income. Health status- mean HgA1c for mother was 8.4%, mean BMI for mothers & daughter of 34.9 & 35.4 respectively at time of enrollment. Satisfaction with Unidas Program- 94% reported enjoyed study participation, 82% reported easier way to participate, 92% reported making healthier food choices, 87% reported improvement with exercise program.	16 wks behavior wt. loss intervention, 4 group meetings Suggestion of similar programs development to reduce obesity

Notes. DM = diabetes mellitus; DPP = diabetes prevention program; B/P = blood pressure; BMI = body mass index; IV = independent variable; DV = dependent variable; YRS = years; WT = weight; WKS = weeks; HbA1c = glycosylated hemoglobin.

Table 4. Group Teaching

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Conclusion/Study Limitations
To compare group versus one-to-one prenatal care and how these approaches affect perinatal outcomes, psychological measures and satisfaction, labor and birth, and provider satisfaction. (Homer et al., 2012)	Systematic Review of RCTs Variables: Group, conventional, & CenteringPregnancy interventions	2012 <i>n</i> = 1369 women Conventional, one-to-one provider or individual Group CenteringPregnancy, 8-12 women per group of similar GA. Meet 8-10 times during pregnancy, 90-120 minutes per session NSW, Australia	2 RCTs measures, preterm births, LBW, perinatal mortality, NICU admissions, & breastfeeding initiation Psychological measures & satisfaction Labor & birth outcomes Effects of group versus one-to-one care provider satisfaction with prenatal care	No statistically significance from both groups with preterm births or LBW from 2 RCTs. Group versus conventional, few differences in clinical outcomes with 2 RCTs in USA (risk ratio (RR) 0.87; 95% confidence interval (CI) 0.47 to 1.60; two trials; N = 1315) Group prenatal care were more likely to initiate breastfeeding 1 group trial had high satisfaction rate of group prenatal care (<i>n</i> = 993)	Small number of studies Further research using CenteringPregnancy model internationally
Conduct focus groups with underprivileged MA that live within U.S. Mexico border communities to identify barriers that impede healthy lifestyles to prevent diabetes. (Brown et al, 2018)	Qualitative	<i>n</i> = 27 MA diagnosed with prediabetes or T2DM Males & females, foreign born & Spanish speaking 3 scheduled groups, 7-12 informants per	Structured interview questions Cultural considerations: Food, & exercise Barriers to: Healthy eating, exercise, technology	Importance of cultural food Priority issues for diabetes prevention, need to learn to prepare healthier food, & track intake of calories Main barriers to healthier lifestyles: Costly food that is healthy, fatigue from	Focus groups preferred due to community buy in & participants build on others' responses in social supportive environment Predominately female sample

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Conclusion/Study Limitations
		group, & 2-hour sessions Texas, USA	use, health care access, & healthier lifestyles Recommendations for intervention: Food, exercise, technology motivation, diabetes, & general observations Characteristics questionnaire	busy schedules & working many jobs, culture views of exercise as waste and valuable time & fear of deportation Female (77.8%), & born outside U.S. (70.4) Prediabetes or T2DM (70.4%) Spanish speaking only (67%) Attended previous DSME programs (63%)	Lifestyles need regular assessment & implement changes to make a difference for selected population Use of <i>Promotoras</i> (community health worker) mention in study
Assess the impact of CenteringPregnancy versus traditional prenatal care and PP follow-up for GDM Hispanic women. (Schellinger et al., 2017)	Retrospective cohort study Controlled group, one-to-one prenatal care	2010-2015 $n = 460$ GDM 203 = CenteringPregnancy prenatal care 257 = individual prenatal care Indianapolis, USA	Characteristics of study population Perinatal & NB outcomes PP visits BF initiation & family planning methods	CenteringPregnancy group were more likely to complete PP glucose testing compared to individual (83.6 vs. 60.7 %, respectively; $p < 0.001$), higher rate of BF initiation (91.0 vs. 69.4 %; $p < 0.001$), higher rates of strictly BF at PP visit (63.1 vs. 46.3 %; $p = 0.04$), less likely require medications in pregnancy (30.2 vs. 42.1 %; $p = 0.009$), & less likely to be induced (34.5 vs. 46.2 %; $p = 0.014$).	Group prenatal care had better outcomes for Hispanic GDM women All classes were given in Spanish Heterogenous controlled population

Notes. GA = gestational age; RCTs = randomized controlled trials; LBW = low birth weight; NICU = neonatal intensive care unit; MA = Mexican Americans; T2DM = type 2 diabetes mellitus; DSME = diabetes self-management education; GDM = gestational diabetes mellitus; PP = postpartum; NB = newborn; BF = breastfeeding.

Table 5. Diabetes Interventions for Minority Patients (non-English speaking)

Purpose/Author	Design/Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Results or Findings	Conclusion/Study Limitations
To utilize the concept of compadrazgo kinship in Mexican American women's psychosocial experience with social support known as comadres. (Gill-Hopple, 2010)	Grounded theory Survey responses on process of becoming a comadre and dimensions of the relationship.	Sample: 23 21 females 2 males (1 community leader & 1 priest) Age: 29-83 Midwestern community Wichita, Kansas	Interview guide- 11 open-ended questions Demographics characteristics data sheet	Madrinas were mostly chosen for Baptismal $n = 17.81\%$ & First Communing $n = 9.43\%$ Majority were Catholic Christian Basic Social Process represented two main categories: 1) "Sister of the Heart" (sharing values, role-modeling, family bonding 2) "Making the Second Home" for the child.	Strengths: Questions were standard and simple. Limitations: Interviewer/researcher was Caucasian English speaking. Need for Spanish speaking only participants More studies needed comparing secular vs. spiritual responsibilities and expectations of compadrazgo
Primary prevention program (Dulce Mothers) designed for low income Spanish Speaking Hispanics with history of GDM to reduce incidence of T2DM and CVD (Philis-Tsimikas et al., 2014)	Single-group pre-post design	N = 84 Hispanic women, 18-45 of age, with past hx. of GDM in past 3 years San Diego, CA	Self-report questionnaires at baseline, 3 months, and 6 months Between baseline and 3rd month participants attended a 2-hour Dulce Mothers intervention weekly (8 wks total)	T2DM (HbA1c $\geq 6.5\%$) throughout 6 months' period Significant improvements with lipid levels (7 and 14 mg/dL), B/P (< 2 mmHg in DBP) and lifestyle behaviors	16.5% dropped out due to lack of transportation or returned to Mexico Peer educator led model Inclusion criteria did not include obesity/overweight Medications were not monitored

			Self-report outcomes: Exercise, fat intake, perceived health, fatalistic beliefs, and diabetes cultural beliefs		
			Clinical measures: HbA1c, cholesterol, B/P, and BMI		
To test the use of <i>Cafecitos</i> and <i>Telenovelas</i> interventions to Mexican American (MA) elders and caregivers to use HCS. (Crist, 2005)	Pilot sample	3 samples in 3 settings for <i>Cafecitos</i> N = 43 4 samples in 4 settings N = 55 > 55 years or older, mixed genders & predominately Spanish speaking only All samples were from local community and wellness centers, or neighborhood associations meetings Tucson, AZ	Changes in knowledge and attitudes to utilize HCS Cafecitos- audiotaped, notes Telenovelas- anecdotally quantitatively & Pre and post 12-item questionnaire in Spanish or English language	Small sample to derive statistical significance. Pre- & post-tests presented trends toward increase knowledge <i>Cafecitos</i> Setting 1, increased knowledge that HCS exist Setting 2, increased knowledge of HCS Setting 3, strong expectations of familism for care <i>Telenovelas</i> Open to learning and hearing about HCS	<i>Telenovelas</i> had better outcomes. Engaged audience more in dialogue. Used 4 acts, 8 minutes each. Anglo facilitator may have decreased participants to more dialogue <i>Telenovela</i> alone may increase dialogue

Notes. BMI = body mass index; CVD = cardiovascular disease; GDM = gestational diabetes mellitus; HbA1c = glycosylated hemoglobin; HCS = home care services; hx. = history; T2DM = type 2 diabetes mellitus; wks